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Techno-economical analysis of Ground Source Heat Pump system (GSHPs) for residential application in remote northern Ontario region

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Abstract

Ground Source Heat Pump Systems (GSHPs) are a clean and low-carbon source of shallow geothermal renewable energy for space heating, space cooling, and water heating applications. The present study is a technical and economical assessment of GSHP systems for space heating, cooling, and water heating applications in the cold, remote regions in northern Ontario. It evaluates the cost and environmental benefits of vertical and horizontal GSHPs in comparison to conventional fossil fuel based systems. A real house design from Ontario, Canada is selected for this study in place of a hypothetical house design to investigate the feasibility of installation of the GSHP system for the northern Ontario region. The summer and winter outdoor temperature for the selected region are 12 °C and -22 °C, respectively. As real house design is chosen, the results provide an economical and technical basis for making the investment decisions to implement GSHPs as low carbon and feasible alternative to conventional fossil fuel based systems. The study also discusses the environmental benefits of implementing a GSHP system instead of a conventional fossil fuel based system in terms of reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emission specifically from natural gas based space heating and hot water application in the challenging remote cold regions of Ontario.

1. Introduction

Climate change effects are apparent across, Canada in the form of thawing, ice melting, warmer winter, coastal erosion, and many other climate alterations. Northern Ontario is no exception and climate change effects can be found alarming in the cities of northern Ontario. For example, the “hub of great lakes”, Sault Ste Marie region has reported severe climate change impacts in the form of water quality decline due to sediment washing (offshore soil washed into the waterbody due to heavy rain). Thunder Bay has recorded 1.4°C of increase in maximum winter temperature and reduction in total annual

precipitation by 160 mm over the length of 60 years (OCCIAIR, 2010). Such climate change impacts have the potential to seriously influence the living condition, water resources, tourism, recreation, and various other aspects of northern Ontario in the coming years. Therefore, the northern Ontario region which constitutes more than 80% of the total land area of Ontario, requires structured climate change actions to minimize GHG emissions and consequently reduce the forthcoming climate change impacts. When it comes to GHG emission, the residential sector of Ontario solely consumes 36.2% of total energy use and produces 18.1% of the total GHG emission in Canada (NRCAN, 2020a). In the residential sector of Ontario, space heating accounts for 61.7 % of total energy use and 73.2 % of equivalent CO₂ emission (NRCAN, 2020a). It is evident that space heating application is a significant contributor to the overall GHG emission in Ontario. To reduce GHG emissions from the residential sector of Ontario, choosing renewable energy based space heating technology as an alternative to conventional space heating technology, can be an effective step.

Ground source heat pump systems (GSHPs) are widely accepted renewable energy option which uses ground as a heat source and sink for space heating and cooling applications. Various studies have explored the application of GSHP in cold climates (Kegel et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2015; Ozyurt & Ekinici, 2011; Rad et al., 2013; Sarbu & Sebarchievici, 2014). Ozyurt & Ekinici (2011) have experimentally shown the viability of the GSHP system in the cold region of Turkey, where the minimum and maximum outdoor temperature was -16.9 °C and 17.3 °C, respectively. Inalli & Esen (2004) have conducted an experimental study to understand the influence of depth of borehole heat exchanger, flow rate of heat carrier fluid, and sewer water on the performance of horizontal GSHP system installed for space heating application. Kjellsson et al. (2010) have studied the GSHP system in combination with the solar collector for heating in Sweden and discussed the significance of borehole size in the context of system cost and thermal load variation. Liu

et al. (2015) have conducted a feasibility study of the GSHP system in the cold climate of three cities in China and emphasized the importance of long-term simulation analysis to determine the feasibility of the GSHP installation in heating dominated region. In this study, the selected cities typically experience the minimum outdoor temperature as low as $-24.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Wang et al. (2013) have evaluated the performance of the GSHP system installed in clay soil for space heating purposes. Kegel et al. (2016) have studied the performance of the GSHP system in the cold Canadian far north location as an alternative to oil-fired boiler heating system and recommended the integration of conventional GSHP system with solar energy to attain better performance and minimize ground thermal imbalance. Emmi et al. (2015) have studied control strategies for solar assisted GSHP systems in cold climates to achieve better efficiency. The feasibility of GSHP in Ontario has been studied (Al-haq, 2017) and comparatively more GSHP applications can be found in southern Ontario. As northern Ontario is notably colder than southern Ontario and experiences extreme weather conditions, a feasibility study of GSHP technology specific to the northern Ontario region is required. This study proposes an application of the GSHP system in the northern Ontario residential sector for space heating and cooling applications. In this work, energy simulation of a selected actual house design is performed to generate thermal load. This thermal load is then used for GSHP design to analyze the feasibility of GSHP system in the cold northern Ontario region.

2. Method

First, the heating and cooling load for the residential two-storey detached house in the cold climate of northern Ontario is calculated using the meteorological condition and house design details. The calculated thermal load from the energy simulation step is then used as an input in GSHP design simulation software to get the operation response of the GSHP system based on selected design conditions, input parameters, and selected geosystem unit. The output in the terms of coefficient of performance (COP), energy efficiency ratio (EER), average system efficiency, energy consumption, and operating costs are obtained. The output from the GSHP design step is then used to analyze the feasibility of the GSHP system in the northern Ontario region.

2.1. Energy simulation of the house

For energy simulation, an actual house design is selected and modeled in the climate condition of one of the cities from the region of northern Ontario. The energy simulation is performed using BEopt (2.8.0.0) (NREL, 2018) software tool which is optimal building design

software, it uses the EnergyPlus simulation engine to conduct detailed building energy analysis for given construction characteristics and location as an input. The actual house design, standard planning, and construction material details are adapted from Rad et al. (2013) and modeled in BEopt (2.8.0.0) under the climate condition of Thunder Bay. The selected house is two-storey detached construction with a living area of 498 m^2 . In the BEopt (2.8.0.0) software, Parametric Mode is used and thermal load for the selected house design is calculated for different heating setpoints varying from $21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ keeping the cooling set point at $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The simulation end-use output generated by the energy analysis provided the heating and cooling load of the house model. The thermal load output calculated from the condition with the heating setpoint of $21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the cooling setpoint of $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is used further in the GSHP design step. The heating and cooling load output from the building energy simulation step is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. House thermal load output and thermal design details.

Thermal parameters	Value
Total heating load (MMBtu/year)	222.37
Total cooling load (MMBtu/year)	13.2
Maximum heating load (Btu)	65373
Maximum cooling load (Btu)	283
Heating set point	$21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Cooling set point	$24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
1% Cooling design temperature	$28\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
97% Heating design temperature	$-31\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Hot water setpoint	$54\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

2.2. GSHP design

The maximum and total thermal load output for the selected house model generated from BEopt (2.8.0.0) software were used as input parameters in GSHP system design. In this study, GSHP design was performed using GeoSmart design studio (GDS) software (Marco, 2018). The input values for the GSHP component sizing were heating load, cooling load; heating, cooling, and hot water setpoints; climate condition, location specific utility rates of each fuel-in-use. For these input values, GSHP components were determined by choosing the appropriate geosystem unit, and ground loop characteristics. In the ground loop characteristics, GSHP design parameters such as loop type (horizontal and vertical), soil type, depth of borehole (vertical GSHP), or length of the trench (horizontal GSHP) were selected. Multiple GSHP design configurations were then analyzed to find the most suitable design in terms of system performance and economy for the given thermal load and climate conditions.

To begin with GSHP component sizing, Thunder Bay was chosen as the site location in the GDS (2.1.0.30) software.

GDS (2.1.0.30) software has location specific ground thermal data stored for various cities including Thunder Bay. The thermal load generated in the energy simulation step, heating setpoint, and cooling setpoint were then entered as an input. Under the hot water section, hot water setpoint and the number of users are the input values. This was followed by providing utility rates for various energy sources in use. Utility rates of energy types such as electricity, propane, natural gas, and furnace oil were collected for Thunder Bay to estimate the operation cost (NRCan, 2020b). To compare the horizontal and vertical GSHP system with conventional fossil fuel based system, the three systems were analyzed separately in detail. For each system various capacities of GSHP unit, water heater type and ground loop configurations were analyzed and compared to find the most efficient and economical system combination which can provide required thermal load. The details of input parameters and characteristics of suitable ground loop configuration selected after several analyses are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Design details of the selected configuration.

GDS component	Selected type
Vertical geosystem unit	VI series variable capacity (4 ton)
Vertical ground loop type	1 U-Bend- 3.175 (cm)
Borehole length	220 (m)
Soil thermal conductivity	2.42 (W/m·K)
Soil diffusivity	0.089 (m ² /day)
Horizontal geosystem unit	VI series variable capacity (3 ton)
Hori. ground loop type	Horizontal4pipe-1.91 (cm)
Trench length	274 (m)
Soil thermal conductivity	1.29 (W/m·K)
Soil diffusivity	0.056 (m ² /day)
Fossil Furnace unit	
AC unit	13 SEER/ Single stage R22
Heating furnace	Boiler-Gas 90% spark

3. Results

In this study, the selected actual house design was modeled in the climate of Thunder Bay for building energy calculation. The calculated heating and cooling load generated from the energy simulation step are shown in Table 1. The monthly heating load of the house peaked in the month of January (65,373 Btu), whereas the cooling load was at the peak in the month of July (283 Btu). As northern Ontario region is colder in comparison to the southern Ontario, a substantially lower cooling load was generated for the selected climate condition. From the hourly and annual thermal load output, it is apparent that Thunder Bay experiences an extremely cold winter and has high heating load demand throughout

the year in comparison to the cooling load. The technical and economical analysis in GDS (2.1.0.30) provides output in terms of coefficient of performance (COP) for heating system, the energy efficiency ratio (EER) for the cooling system, system average efficiency for hot water unit, and operating annual cost for each selected system. These performance indicator outputs are generated for several analyses conducted for each system type as discussed in section 2.2. For the vertical GSHP system, the geosystem unit with the capacity of 2 ton, 3 ton, and 4 ton were investigated for the calculated thermal load. For 2 ton capacity geosystem unit, a single U-tube heat exchanger of depth 110 m is selected. Though this system was most economical due to the lower capacity unit and least borehole depth, it is inefficient to provide the total thermal demand of the house. A similar trend was observed for the system with 3 ton capacity geosystem unit and 165 m deep borehole equipped with a single U-tube heat exchanger. For the system with 4 ton capacity geosystem unit, 220 m deep borehole with a single U-tube heat exchanger, the thermal output was adequate for thermal load demand. The 4 ton capacity system offers COP of 4.13 for the heating unit and EER of 32.31 for the cooling unit with an annual operating cost of \$921. Considering 8000\$ per ton of investment cost for vertical GSHP installation, the capital cost for 4 ton capacity vertical GSHP system will be 32000\$ (Al-haq, 2017). A similar investigation is carried out for horizontal GSHP system in which system capacities of 2 to 4 tons were studied. For 2 ton horizontal geosystem unit, the total length of the ground loop is 183 m and this system was inadequate to provide the required thermal load. The horizontal system of 3 tons capacity with a total ground loop length of 274 m provided an adequate thermal output for the required thermal demand. The 3 ton capacity horizontal GSHP system, offers COP of 4.24 for the heating unit, EER of 35.10 for the cooling unit with an annual operating cost of \$905. Considering 5000\$ per ton of investment cost for horizontal GSHP installation, the capital cost for 3 ton capacity horizontal GSHP system will be 15000\$ (Al-haq, 2017). The selected conventional fossil fuel based system (**Table 2**), offers an efficiency of 87.25% for the heating system and EER of 30.8 for the cooling system unit with a total annual operating cost of \$1655. The installation cost for the conventional fossil fuel based system will be significantly lesser than the vertical and horizontal GSHP system. Natural gas is the fuel type used in the conventional fossil fuel based system which directly contributes to GHG emission. A standard conversion coefficient is used to find equivalent CO₂ emission for the quantity of fuel used in conventional fossil fuel based system (EIA, 2016). The natural gas consumption in the conventional fossil fuel

based system is estimated to be 1962 m³ which is converted to equivalent CO₂ emission using the conversion coefficient. The equivalent CO₂ emission conversion estimates annual emission of around 4 tons of CO₂ from the conventional fossil fuel based system. This GHG emission can be reduced if conventional fossil fuel based system is replaced by environment friendly GSHP system.

4. Conclusions

This study aims to analyze the technical and economical feasibility of vertical and horizontal GSHP systems for space conditioning application in comparison to conventional fossil fuel based systems for the cold northern Ontario region. The performance and cost calculated from this study support the GSHP system as an efficient, economical, and environment friendly alternative to the conventional fossil fuel based system. The excellent performance is recorded for both vertical and horizontal GSHP systems for heating and cooling applications. The estimated operating cost for both vertical and horizontal GSHP systems is lower than the operating cost of conventional fossil fuel based system by a significant difference. In addition to this, the GSHP system offers a GHG emission-free system in contrast to conventional fossil fuel based system. The equivalent CO₂ emission estimated from the natural gas based conventional heating system can completely be eliminated if it is replaced by environment friendly GSHP system. It is recommended that the feasibility of the GSHP system needs to be explored rigorously for the northern Ontario region by taking into account the meteorological conditions of more than one city of the northern Ontario region. From the calculated heating and cooling load, the ground thermal imbalance is expected in a long-term GSHP operation for the northern Ontario region. In order to capture the influence of ground thermal imbalance on the system performance, it is required to study the long-term operation of the GSHP system. From the study, the GSHP system has been found to be a suitable environment friendly space conditioning technology.

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Geothermal Usage: Heat Transfer in Fractured Granite

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Abstract

Shallow geothermal boreholes can be used for heat extraction within low permeable hard rock formations such as granite. Presence of fractures in granite bedrock impacts the heat storage and transfer capabilities during geothermal usage. This study evaluates the impact of energy balancing by charging granite bedrock during summer and by heat extraction during winter near Winnipeg, MB. Nine major simulation models for a single borehole were performed with horizontal, vertical, and no fracture conditions. The simulation results show that granite bedrock could be heated using a single borehole heat exchanger (BHE) during summer, and the heat could subsequently be extracted over the winter. The heat extraction in winter without adding any heat in summer showed that heat extraction was overall less compared to heat extraction in winter when the bedrock is charged in summer. The results also showed that the fractures acted as the main heat storage during the heating of the granite. However, the increase in the outlet temperature of the BHE was not significant as the borehole depth was limited to 20 m. Further studies would be required to perform sensitivity analysis with additional boreholes and different depths to assess the feasibility of borehole heat exchanger in shallow depth.

1. Introduction

Climate change has become one of the most crucial issues in the recent era, and the reduction of the utilization of fossil fuel energy is taken into consideration (Bae et al., 2018; Kumari et al., 2017). Sustainable developments are necessary to overcome the crisis of climate change. The increasing demand for fossil fuel to generate energy can be mitigated by utilizing renewable energy technologies such as geothermal heat extraction from the shallow or deep bedrock aquifers (granite) by BHE systems (Diersch et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2020). Geothermal heat extraction is the process of extracting heat from the shallow ground (less than 400m) or deep ground (more than 400 m) by using BHE (Agemar et al., 2014; Guo et al., 2018). Electricity can be generated by exploiting this extraction heat and can be used for space heating and cooling purposes. Granite formation can be commonly found in

the Canadian Shield and can be used as a geothermal source to extract heat (e.g., Wang and Konietzky, 2019). The geo-exchange potential within the rocks varies with their crystal structure and composition, and mechanical properties (Zhao, 2016). Plevová et al. (2016) analyzed the thermal expansion behavior of granites. Miranda et al. (2020) characterized the thermophysical properties of surficial granites as a potential geothermal resource of remote northern areas. Thermomechanical properties of granite at elevated temperatures and numerical simulation of thermal cracking were assessed by Wang & Konietzky (2019). Di Sipio et al. (2013) studied rock thermal conductivity as the main parameter for geothermal numerical models.

The installation of ground source heat pump (GSHP) systems require excavation, drilling, or coring the borehole. The installation of ground heat exchangers may become expensive due to geological conditions (Bae et al., 2018). Different Borehole Heat Exchanger (BHE) systems can be applied for heat extraction from the ground (Diersch et al., 2010).

Geothermal technologies can be used to extract energy from thousands of feet below the earth with the presence of three primary conditions such as heat, fluid, and natural permeability (Guo et al., 2018). Heat can be extracted or injected based on utilizing modes such as heating or cooling mode (Hecht-Mendez et al., 2010). As a result, cold or warm plumes occur due to the fluctuation of the temperatures within the subsurface of the bedrock or soil. These fluctuations occur because of the lateral conduction and convection heat transport processes when the groundwater flows from one direction to the other (Hecht-Mendez et al., 2010).

Fractures can influence the borehole heat exchangers' temperature in the rocks (Dehkordi et al., 2015). The presence of fractures in the rock enhances the temperature within the borehole heat exchanger and rocks' subsurface due to warm water movements into the fractures (Dehkordi et al., 2015; Martinez et al., 2014). Hence, groundwater flow improves the thermal conductivity and heat transport in the fractured rock, and thereby, shallow BHEs can also extract heat from the subsurface of the rock (less than 400 m). (Wang et al., 2009; Agemar et al.,

2014). Nordell et al. (1986) observed the impacts of fractures in a pilot borehole field and concluded that fracturing could reduce the geothermal system's installation cost by 10% to 15%. Dehkordi et al. (2015) developed a finite element model that showed that the temperature of borehole heat exchangers and subsurface of the rock depends on the fracture's aperture and distance of fracture from the BHE.

The project aims to explore the potential for geothermal usage from shallow depth (20 m) borehole heat exchangers in the Canadian Shield. The study's objective is to simulate the two cases of BHEs systems considering without and with energy balancing (Case 1 and Case 2). The explanation for the Case 1 and Case 2 can be found in the Methods section.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area is Pointe du Bois, a small community located northeast of Winnipeg, Manitoba. Pointe du Bois near Lac du Bonnet, Manitoba, has a hydroelectric generating station (at 50°18'13"N 95°32'24"W) owned by Manitoba Hydro. Pointe du Bois Generating Station is located along the Winnipeg River. Point du Bois is situated in the Canadian Shield, where bedrock outcrops and shallow bedrock with dry sand cover can be frequently found. The area has been selected to assess geothermal energy potential using shallow depth borehole heat exchangers because of the presence of a major river and shallow bedrock. Borehole heat exchangers have the potential to serve as a source for space heating and cooling for small homes.

2.2 Scenarios

In Case 1, the borehole heat exchanger was modeled in granite with three variable fracture scenarios such as no fracture, vertical fracture, and horizontal fracture. A closed-loop double U loop system was modeled within the borehole heat exchanger to simulate the heat extraction from granite with naturally stable temperature (without energy balancing) for various fracture scenarios during the winter months.

On the other hand, in Case 2, the borehole heat exchanger was modeled in granite with similar variable fracture scenarios such as no fracture, vertical fracture, and horizontal fracture. An open-loop borehole heat exchanger was modeled to simulate granite charging by circulating warm water pumped into the borehole from the river throughout the summer months. A closed-loop double U loop system was then modeled within the borehole heat exchanger to simulate the heat extraction

from granite with higher temperatures due to summer heating for various fracture scenarios during winter months. The key objective of Case 2 was to evaluate the advantage of charging the granite (energy balancing) over the summer months.

2.3 Data and Assumptions

In this study, the key objective is to assess the relative advantage of energy balancing for geothermal heat extraction from a shallow borehole heat exchanger with a maximum depth of 20 m. The domain temperature was assumed 6.5°C and remained constant throughout the year for the study area. Therefore, the initial domain temperature was selected as 6.5°C for model development. It was also considered that during the summer season, water was circulated through the BHE from the Winnipeg River for injecting heat surrounding the subgrade (granite domain). Summer water temperature information was unavailable hence assumed to be 25°C. Refrigerant temperature for circulation through winter was considered to be 1°C (inlet temperature of BHE). The groundwater table was assumed to be 6 m below the ground surface. The stratigraphy was assumed to consist of 2 m of dry sand cover overlaying 4 m of dry granite.

Realistic ambient temperature data was collected from the Government of Canada website (climate.weather.gc.ca). In order to reduce the computation time, average temperatures of May 2019 to April 2020 were taken.

2.4 Numerical Modeling

Simulations were carried out using FEFLOW 7.0 software. Coupled 1D line element BHE, 2D discrete fracture model, and 3D continuum model approach were used for the modeling.

A rectangular domain was modeled with dimensions (100 m x 100 m). The model was developed comprising eleven slices (2 m) and meshed consisting of 34290 triangular random-sized elements. The initial time step length was selected to be 0.5 days, and the final simulation time was 181.5 days for case 1, and for case 2, the model was run in two steps i) for summer simulation, the duration was 182.5 days, and ii) for winter simulation duration was 181.1 days. For both case 1 and case 2, the vertical fractures, one running east-west and one running north-south, were assigned from slice two to slice eleven (from 2 m to 20 m depth). It is noteworthy to mention that the vertical fracture running east-west was selected to coincide with the borehole, and the vertical fracture running north-south was selected approximately 6 m from the borehole. The two different locations of fractures with respect to boreholes were selected to evaluate the

effect of fracture distance on heat transfer. For the horizontal fracture case, two horizontal fractures were assigned on slice five (at depth 8 m) and slice eight (at depth 14 m), respectively. The discrete features were assigned in the model using Hagen- Poiseuille joint face.

The assumed hydraulic conductivity for coarse sand was 8×10^{-3} m/s (Hecht-Mendez et al., 2010), dry granite was 3.3×10^{-6} m/s (Di Sipio et al., 2013), and wet granite was 6×10^{-3} m/s (Cho et al., 2010). The assumed effective porosity for sand was 0.26 (Stephens et al., 1998), dry granite was 0.006, and wet granite was 0.0387 (Di Sipio et al., 2013). The thickness and aperture of the fractures (both horizontal and vertical) were 0.002 m and 0.002 m (Dehkordi et al., 2015), respectively.

The BHE was assigned from the top slice to the bottom slice (at full domain depth). Boundary conditions for flow and heat transport were applied in the model. It was assumed that the direction of the groundwater flow would be from west to east. Therefore, a fixed hydraulic head boundary conditions (Dirichlet type) were set along west and east mesh borders from the fourth slice to the eleventh slice. As a result of setting the fixed hydraulic head from west to east, the hydraulic gradient of 0.01 m/m was incorporated in the model. A constant initial condition of 6.5°C (domain temperature) was set throughout the entire domain for case 1 winter condition and case 2 summer condition. The initial temperature condition for case 2 winter was selected based on the results of case 2 summer conditions so that the domain in case 2 winter represents heated granite from case 2.

The fourth type of heat transport boundary condition (BHE) was applied for the BHE. The inlet temperature of the BHE was assigned as a constant temperature 25°C (Winnipeg River water), and a constant flow rate of $30 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$ was set for the summer season. During the summertime, the temperature was injected into the surrounding domain by a fully coupling model, where heat was exchanged from BHE pipes to grout and grout to the surrounding domain (granite). On the other hand, in winter, a constant temperature of 1°C for the refrigerant was assigned to flow through the borehole heat exchanger with a flow rate of $20 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$. Two observation points were selected at depth 8 m (slice 5) and 12 m (slice 8), respectively, on the domain throughout the different simulations.

In addition, an extensive literature review of relevant studies was performed to select representative parameters for the model development. The depth and diameter of BHE were selected 20 m and 0.1 m for both case 1 and Case 2, respectively. The outer diameter of the pipes was assumed 0.032 m, the thickness of the pipes was assumed

0.0029 m, and the distance between the pipes was assumed 0.042 m for both cases (Diersch et al., 2010). The thermal conductivity of the sand was $0.15 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Dalla et al., 2020), dry and wet granite were 2.8 and $4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively (Di Sipio et al., 2013), water was $0.65 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, pipes were 0.38 (Diersch et al., 2010), grout was $1 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and refrigerant was $0.48 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (FEFLOW default value). The volumetric heat capacity of refrigerant was $4 \times 10^6 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (FEFLOW default value), and water was $4.2 \times 10^6 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Diersch et al., 2010), sand was $0.15 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Dalla et al., 2020), dry granite was $2.4 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Di Sipio et al., 2013) and wet granite was $3 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Bae et al., 2018).

The longitudinal and transverse thermodispersivity of the aquifer for sand were 0.5 m and 0.05 m respectively (Hecht-Mendez et al., 2010); for dry and wet granite, it was assumed 0.5 m and 0.05 m, respectively. For the fractures, the value of the longitudinal and transverse thermodispersivity of the aquifer was assumed the default value of the FEFLOW.

3. Results

Total nine simulations named SIM 1-9 were performed using FEFLOW software to simulate case 1 and case 2. SIMs 1, 2, and 3 were run for case 2 for 182.5 days of summer with a constant inlet temperature 25°C and domain temperature 6.5°C. Similarly, SIMs 4, 5, and 6 were run for case 2 wintertime with inlet temperature of 1°C for 181.5 days where the domain was heated as a result of summer simulations. SIMs 7, 8, and 9 were simulated for case 1, where simulations were run only for wintertime (without energy balancing) for 181.5 days. An outlet temperature time series was obtained for the duration of the simulation. **Table 1** summarizes the final outlet temperature at the end of each simulation.

Table 1. Borehole Heat Exchanger inlet and outlet temperature at the end of the simulation.

Simulation	Fracture	Time	Inlet temperature (°C)	Outlet temperature (°C)
SIM 1	N/A	S	25	24.3
SIM 2	V		25	23.10
SIM 3	H		25	23.65
SIM 4	N/A	W	1	1.90
SIM 5	V		1	0.20
SIM 6	H		1	2.00
SIM 7	N/A		1	1.25
SIM 8	V		1	0.10
SIM 9	H		1	1.40
V = vertical, H = horizontal, S = summer, W = winter				

Fig. 1. Temperature at depth of 8 m at the end of (a) SIM 7, (a) SIM 8 and (c) SIM 9

4. Discussion

The reduction in temperature for summer (SIMs 2 and 3) at the outlet of the boreholes with a fractured domain was found to be larger than boreholes without a fractured domain (SIM 1). A relatively larger reduction in outlet temperature can be seen for the domain with vertical fracture (SIM 2) compared to the domain with horizontal fracture (SIM 3). The vertical fracture runs throughout the entire bedrock depth of the borehole's heat exchanger, and one of the fractures coincides with the borehole. On the other hand, for simulations with the horizontal fracture domain, the fractures are located at a specific depth, and they coincide with the borehole heat exchanger. However, the overall heat loss through the fractures was found to be relatively lower due to the lower specific surface exposed to fracture. Therefore, a larger amount of heat loss throughout the fracture was seen for vertical fracture domains compared to the horizontal fracture domain.

In winter simulations (SIMs 7, 8, and 9), the temperature increase was generally observed in outlet temperatures. However, a decrease in outlet temperature was seen in the case of the vertical domain (SIM 8). The temperature reduction happened due to vertical fracture throughout the length of the fracture where the loss of heat occurred.

The temperature contour distribution for SIMs 1, 4, and 7 where no fracture was present showed a perfect radial distribution of temperature around the borehole as the materials were selected as homogeneous and isotropic (Fig. 1a)). The effect of groundwater flow in the domain

was not prominent as the flow through the porous matrix is insignificant compared to flow through fractures. For SIMs 2, 5, and 8, due to vertical fracture, a temperature concentration along the fractures was observed (Fig. 1b)). Moreover, the effect of groundwater flow through the fractures was observed on the temperature contour as the heat plumes were shifted towards the east where the groundwater was flowing. For SIMs 3, 6, and 9, the temperature contour showed an apparent heat plume shifted towards the east (Fig. 1c)). The horizontal fractures were located at slices 5 and 8. Therefore, active groundwater flow through the horizontal fracture caused the heat plume to shift eastward.

The overall higher temperature in the domain was found at the end of winter simulations (SIMs 4, 5, and 6), with energy balancing compacted to winter simulations without energy balancing (SIMs 7, 8, and 9).

5. Conclusions

The study revealed that the warmer temperatures of the Winnipeg river water could be used to circulate through borehole heat exchangers to heat granite bedrock. The simulation results also revealed that a single borehole heat exchanger can be exploited to inject the heat into granite bedrock in the summer and extract the heat in the winter. However, the amount of heat output from a single borehole may not be adequate to serve space heating and cooling purpose. Overall, an increase in the outlet temperature of the BHE was not significant as the borehole was shallow with a depth limited to (20 m).

On the other hand, groundwater flow impacts the heat transfer within the fracture and porous media. Heat plume towards the direction of flow was observed during the simulations.

Fractures at the vicinity of the boreholes have an impact on heat loss and heat gain through boreholes. Fractures accommodating active groundwater flow may negatively impact the performance of a borehole heat exchanger as groundwater can transfer the heat from the borehole heat exchanger farther. However, the fractures may also act as heat storage during the heating of granite if they are not directly connected with active groundwater flow.

An overall benefit of heating granite in summer can be seen from the results of the study.

Further simulations should be carried out with the higher number of borehole heat exchangers connected in series and parallel to assess the domain heating capability in summer and heat extraction capability in winter. Furthermore, higher mesh refinement should be used for more accurate results. A larger domain should be used for

simulation to avoid heat loss through the boundary of the domain. Sensitivity analysis should be carried out for the borehole heat exchangers' performance with varying depths of boreholes. Fracture is a major driving factor for the efficient operation of BHE. Therefore, various arrangements of fractures should be incorporated in the model to assess the heat storage or heat loss effect on the BHE and the impact on the performance of BHE.

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Life cycle cost analysis of heating system alternatives for residential buildings in Northern Québec (Nunavik, Canada)

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Abstract

Due to its remoteness, extreme weather conditions, limited local energy availability, low population, and limited energy-transportation infrastructure, the region of Nunavik, located in the northernmost part of Québec (Canada), is fully dependent on imported refined petroleum products, mainly diesel, for both their electricity and heating needs, leading to one of the highest energy costs in the country. In this project, building energy simulations were conducted using SIMEB and RETScreen softwares in order to estimate the heating needs of a residential building located in the northern remote community of Umiujaq. The simulations were developed considering a 252 m² one-floor residential house with 5 occupants. Several heating alternatives were studied to meet the heating needs of the building to reduce dependence on fossil fuels, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and heating cost through the application of wood pellet boilers and geothermal heat pumps compared to conventional oil furnaces. An economic analysis was carried out through the development of a life cycle cost analysis (LCCA) of each alternative considering environmental, technical, and economic issues. Preliminary simulation results give a residential building energy intensity of 353 kWh/m². The LCCA analysis shows that the mix of heating systems like geothermal heat pumps, biomass, and solar PV represents interesting heating alternatives for Northern Québec with a Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) that varies from 0.13 to 0.49 \$/kWh depending on the mix of the technologies and their contribution in the heating needs, in comparison with 0.21 \$/kWh of the conventional heating system currently used based on diesel, that is heavily subsidized.

1. Introduction

Arctic and subarctic regions of Canada, such as the territories of Yukon, Northwest Territories, Nunavut, Nunavik (northern Québec), Nunatsiavut (northern Labrador) and the northernmost parts of western provinces until Ontario, form a different region in terms of energy use. The geographic size, remoteness, extreme

weather conditions, limited local energy availability, low population, and limited energy-transportation infrastructure together reduce the energy and fuel supply options for communities. Since the 1950s, some of these regions have depended on fossil fuels (mainly diesel) for both their electricity and heating needs. Although this fuel is subsidized, the energy costs in these communities is one of the highest in the country (NEB, 2016; Cherniak et al., 2015).

In the province of Quebec, efforts to promote an energy transition was included in the Plan Nord in 2011 by the government of Quebec, a strategy that seeks to encourage the development of northern Quebec that is above the 49th degree of latitude. One objective of this strategy is to support projects in the northern communities to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy sources (Société du Plan Nord, 2015; Gunawan et al., 2020). The development of such projects represents high financial risks due to the large investments required. Therefore, an adequate economic feasibility analysis is essential to facilitate decision-making on the energy alternative to be used and to ensure the success of the project throughout its useful life.

Recently, several studies (; Cherniak et al., 2015; Belzile et al., 2017; Yan et al., 2019; Gunawan et al., 2020) were carried out to reach better energy independence and security for isolated regions of Canada. However, on several occasions, energy sources and technologies are evaluated under different models and methodologies, which can make it difficult to identify optimal technical, economic and environmental alternatives.

In this research, a preliminary building energy simulation of different heating systems alternatives was developed for a 252 m² residential building in Umiujaq, and these alternatives were evaluated using a preliminary 50-year LCC model. This allowed identifying alternatives representing viable opportunities for the replacement of conventional heating systems.

Study Area

Umiujaq is an Inuit community of about 440 people (Statistics Canada 2016) located north of Tasiujaq Lake (former Guillaume-Delisle Lake) and near the eastern shore of Hudson Bay, a large and shallow intracratonic sea located in the central part of the Canadian Shield.

Geographically, Umiujaq is located in the zone of discontinuous permafrost that is currently degrading in the area due to the warming climate (Wang et al., 2020). Lithalsas (mineral permafrost mounds), permafrost plateaus (wide and elongated mineral permafrost landforms), palsas (permafrost mounds with a peat cover), and peat plateaus (wide and elongated peaty permafrost landforms) are the dominant permafrost landforms in Umiujaq (Jolivel and Allard, 2013). Most of the village infrastructures are built on raised sandy beaches, a thaw stable material, and other infrastructures such as the roads and airfields lie in part on frozen ice-rich marine sediments, which is a thaw unstable material, outcropping or buried underneath a sand cover (Fortier et al., 2011).

The area of Umiujaq is characterized by a sub-Arctic climate with a mean annual air temperature (MAAT) of approximately -3°C ; the winters are cold and the summers are cool with mean monthly air temperatures of -24°C in January and 10°C in August, respectively. The mean annual precipitation is about 645 mm and most precipitation occurs from July to January. Snowfalls represent about 50% of total precipitation (NordicanaD, 2014; Wang et al., 2020).

2. Methods

Building Energy Simulation

The heating alternatives considered in the building energy simulation have been selected based on previous work (Belzile et al., 2017; Yan et al., 2019; Giordano and Raymond, 2019). The input parameters for identifying the energy needs of a residential building at Umiujaq were taken from the model developed by Gunawan et al. (2020), which consisted in conducting a techno-economic analysis of conventional heating oil furnaces, and ground-coupled heat pumps mixed with PV for a typical residential building at Kuujuaq, Nunavik, Canada. To develop this preliminary simulation, SIMEB was used to define the total heating load (space heating + domestic hot water (DHW)) and the peak load of the simulated building. Then, RETScreen was used to simulate the amount of energy contributed by each of the different technologies and energy sources in the defined heating scenarios.

The heating scenarios considered were:

- CASE 1: Business as usual with fuel oil furnace.
- CASE 2: Ground source heat pump (GSHP) where 100% of the electricity is provided by diesel power plant (DPP) of the autonomous network of Hydro-Québec at Umiujaq.
- CASE 3: Wood pellets boiler.
- CASE 4: GSHP is used until it reaches its full capacity, which is 70% of the peak load. When above, fuel oil furnace is used. 100% of the electricity is provided by DPP.
- CASE 5: GSHP is used until it reaches its full capacity which is 70% of the peak load. When above, fuel oil furnace is used. 100% of the electricity is provided by PV.
- CASE 6.1: GSHP covers 50% of the total heating need, 50% by fuel oil furnace. 100% of the electricity is provided by DPP.
- CASE 6.2: GSHP covers 50% of the total heating need, 50% by fuel oil furnace. 100% of the electricity is provided by solar PV.
- CASE 6.3: GSHP covers 50% of the total heating need, 50% by fuel oil furnace. 70% of the electricity is provided by solar PV while 30% by DPP.
- CASE 7.1: GSHP covers 50% of the peak load, 50% by wood pellets boiler. 100% of the electricity is provided by PV.
- CASE 7.2: GSHP covers 50% of the peak load, 50% by wood pellets boiler. 100% of the electricity is provided by DPP.

In the simulations involving PVs a solar energy storage was not considered. The number of solar PV panels required were calculated by dividing the electricity demand to be met by the solar PV panels by the energy generated from each panel. This was calculated by multiplying the solar PV panel rating, which was assumed at 0.3 kW with 1,072 kWh/kW/year, the solar PV potential in Umiujaq (NRC, 2017)

LCC Analysis

The LCC model developed by Gunawan et al. (2020) was also used for the preliminary economic analysis of conventional and geothermal heating systems. Biomass system cost were taken from CQCH (2018) and Royer (2020).

A net present cost (NPC) and a levelized cost of energy (LCOE) were chosen to evaluate and compare the 50-year life-cycle cost (LCC) of the different heating systems scenarios. The NPC is the present value of all costs generated in the different stages over the project lifetime and can be estimated as following:

$$NPC = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{C_{t,n}}{(1+r)^n}$$

where N is the analysis period (years), n is a time point during the project life-cycle, $C_{t,n}$ is the Net Cash Flow only considering cost in the n year, and r is the discount rate.

The LCOE is the value of the current total cost of building and operating a power generation facility over its lifetime. It allows to directly compare the costs of different energy sources and technologies as it is a cost that is standardized. The calculation of this parameter will be achieved using the following equation:

$$LCOE = \frac{NPC}{\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{E_{t,n}}{(1+r)^n}}$$

where NPC is the Net Present Cost of 50 years LCC, and $E_{t,n}$ is the annual energy output (total energy consumption).

The total cost of the heating system that will be taken into account for the development of the LCCA is:

$$Total\ cost\ (C_t) = Capita\ cost\ (C_c) + Anual\ Cost\ (C_a) + Periodic\ Cost\ (C_p)$$

where *Capita cost* (C_c) is the cost of equipment, initial installation or labour and shipping cost, *Anual Cost* (C_a) is the cost of energy without subsidies (pellets, electricity and/or diesel, maintenance cost, GHG emissions), *Periodic Cost* (C_p) is the cost of equipment to be replaced at the end of its lifetime, installation or labour and shipping cost.

3. Results

The annual heating load of a 252 m² residential building in Umiujaq is 89,219 kWh (space heating + DHW) with an energy intensity of 354.04 kWh/m² and a peak heating load of 21.3 kW.

The results of the 50-years LCCA of the different heating scenarios are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. NPC of different heating scenarios evaluated with the preliminary building simulation. Values are given in thousands of Canadian dollars.

Figure 2. LCOE of different heating scenarios evaluated with the preliminary building simulation.

4. Discussion

It is important to take into account that the preliminary LCC model does not consider within the analysis some costs that could be significant in a detailed technical economic LCCA, which will be developed at a subsequent stage of this research, such as oil spills and soil remediation costs for cases where fuel oil is used, cost of components for photovoltaic systems such as a battery system and solar inverter, among other costs.

Figures 1 and 2 show that CASE 3 (Wood-pellets boiler) is the only case that has a lower NPC and LCOE than CASE 1 (Conventional heating system). In this case, this type of technology represents a reduction of 34.5 tons per year of CO_{2,eq}, from 37.1 tCO_{2,eq} in the conventional case to only 2.6 tCO_{2,eq} in CASE 3. It should be noted that bioenergy, specifically the technology that uses wood pellets as fuel, is considered an emission-neutral technology because biomass wood pellets capture almost the same amount of CO₂ through photosynthesis while growing as is released when biomass is burned (EIA, 2020). CASE 6.2 (GSHP, fuel oil furnace and solar PV) and 7.1 (GSHP, Wood-pellets boiler and solar PV) also represent interesting economic alternatives compared to CASE 1. Of the 3 most economically viable cases previously mentioned (3, 6.2 and 7.1), CASE 7.1 is the alternative that represents the greatest energy independence for the town of Umiujaq, a very important characteristics in isolated areas since they allow greater resilience, as indicated in the SDG 7 and 11 (UN, no date).

CASES 2 and 4 present the highest NPC and LCOE of the simulated alternatives. This is due to the large participation of the GSHP system in covering the energy needs of the building. The most significant costs in the GSHP systems are those associated with well drilling. This is why it is important to carefully define the amount of energy to be provided by the geothermal system, since the more energy provided, the greater the length of the

well and therefore the higher the cost of the system. It is therefore necessary to maintain a balance between the energy savings and security that this technology can provide, and its economic viability. It is important to highlight that although CASE 3 (Wood-pellets boiler) presents the lowest cost of the alternatives simulated, the supply of wood pellets can be a problem in these isolated regions, which is not the case for geothermal.

5. Conclusions

50-years life-cycle cost analysis (LCCA) revealed that there are several heating system alternatives that represent an opportunity to change the replace fuel oil based systems, which favor energy security and independence of these isolated communities and generate less greenhouse gas emissions to the environment.

Higher amount of electricity derived from solar PV panels can result in lower total NPC and LCOE for the cases that consider GSHP systems. However important components of the PV system should be considered in a more detailed LCCA, such as the cost of the inverter and battery system. Other costs such as the oil spills of fuel oil caused by conventional heating technologies and soil remediation costs should also be taken into account in a more detailed economic and environmental analysis.

In further research, an advance energy building simulation and a more detailed LCC Analysis will be carried out considering the most techno-economically viable alternatives identified in the previous step. Results could eventually be extended to similar subarctic settings in Canada and worldwide.

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Least squares deconvolution of experimental thermal response test data to recover short-term transfer function

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Abstract

The short-term transfer function of a geothermal heat exchanger is a key element for the design of a geoexchange system since it allows dynamic simulation of the system. In practice, the transfer function is generated with computing thermal models that emulate the thermal behavior of a ground heat exchanger. However, there is currently no method to directly retrieves the short-term transfer function from an experimental data set provided by a thermal response test. A least squares deconvolution method is proposed for this purpose. The proposed method can be applied to time-varying heating load on the full thermal response test data. Test cases done on noisy synthetic and real data sets were analyzed and showed the robustness of the method. Results indicate that filtering the signal with a single pre-processing step prior to deconvolution allowed to recover a transfer function within a relative error of 1%. Deconvolution being fully data-driven, no analytical model is used to represent the ground heat transfer processes. By avoiding the simplifying assumption of an analytical model, this new method improves the construction of the short-term transfer function and should lead to better simulation of ground source heat pump systems.

1. Introduction

When sizing a Ground Heat Exchanger (GHE), it is common to rely on first-order approximation (FOA) to obtain the thermal parameters of the ground. The original method uses a graphic interpretation method (Mogensen, 1983), but recent research enhanced this approach by also using the temperature derivative (Pasquier, 2018). Instead of estimating the thermal parameters of the ground, it is common to use the g -function proposed by Eskilsson (1987), which describes the long-term thermal behaviour of the GHE. A g -function is a signal that is the equivalent of an impulse function (also named transfer function) and it represents the response of a system to a unit impulse signal at the initial time (Smith, 1999). In practice, it corresponds to the response of a GHE to a constant heat impulse of either 1 °C, 1W or 1W/°C for the duration of the TRT (D. Marcotte & Pasquier, 2014).

The classical g -function can only be applied with large time steps. To consider smaller ones, Yavuzturk & Spitler, 1999 developed a short-time transfer function. The evaluation of these transfer functions received considerable research attention in recent years (Cruz-Peragón et al., 2020; Javed & Claesson, 2011; Pasquier et al., 2018) because they can predict the dynamic thermal evolution of the geothermal system. This effect is crucial when considering the transient heat demand from the building and outside temperature variations. Short-term g -functions (STgFs) are usually retrieved with the interpretation of data sets obtained during a thermal response test (TRT). The interpretation models are either analytical or numerical.

Using analytical equations to represent the STgF leads to model errors, added to the usual errors encountered in a TRT (Witte, 2013). Hence, using directly the experimental data to extract the STgF is advantageous as it avoids incorporating model errors. To this regard, a precedent contribution used a FOA to extract the thermal parameters of the ground and then compute the STgF (Cruz-Peragón et al., 2020). Also, a logarithmic thinned time selection of the experimental data was used in to recover a temperature transfer function (Beier, 2020). However, no proposed method uses the entire data set of a TRT to acquire the STgF.

Obtaining the STgF with the entire data set of a TRT is akin to a deconvolution problem. The aim of this paper is to present a regularized, weighted least squares deconvolution algorithm that can be applied to time-varying heat flux to recover the STgF of a GHE.

2. Methods

The convolution equation can be expressed in the time domain by Eq. 2.1 (Pasquier et al., 2018):

$$T_{out}(t_i) - T_0 = (f * g)(t_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i f(t_j)g(t_{i-j+1}) \quad 2.1$$

where T_{out} [°C] is the outlet GHE fluid temperature, T_0 [°C] is the undisturbed ground temperature, g [-] is the

unknown borehole outlet STgF to be evaluated in the deconvolution process and f [°C] is the incremental heat load function that can be calculated with Eq. 2.2:

$$f(t) = \Delta T(t_i) - \Delta T(t_{i-1}) = \frac{Q(t_i) - Q(t_{i-1})}{V(t_i) C_m \rho_f} \quad 2.2$$

where Q [W] is the heat flux injected or extracted from the circulating fluid, \dot{V} [m³·s⁻¹] is the fluid circulating flow rate (which can also be taken as constant), C_m [J·kg⁻¹·K⁻¹] is the specific heat capacity of the fluid and ρ_f [kg·m⁻³] is the density of the fluid.

Eq. 2.1 can be expressed as a matrix multiplication representing the solution of a linear system of equations, with F a Toeplitz triangular inferior matrix composed of the vector f .

$$\Delta T = F \cdot \hat{g} \quad 2.3$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta T(t_1) \\ \Delta T(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ \Delta T(t_n) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f(t_1) & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ f(t_2) & f(t_1) & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & f(t_2) & \ddots & 0 \\ f(t_n) & \cdots & \cdots & f(t_1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{g}(t_1) \\ \hat{g}(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{g}(t_n) \end{bmatrix} \quad 2.4$$

The linear system of equations 2.3 has n unknown and n equations. It can then be solved directly. However, since experimental data have reading errors and \hat{g} has intrinsic properties, a common method to solve Eq. 2.3 is to solve the least squares between the left and right side of the equation with added constraints (BniLam & Al-Khoury, 2020; Zhang et al., 2019). Hence, the problem tries to minimize the objective function:

$$\hat{g} = \arg \min_g \|(f * g) - \Delta T\|_2^2 \quad 2.5$$

It is common to add a regularization term to ensure smoothness of the response function, like the time derivative of the evaluated function, as described at Eq. 2.6:

$$\hat{g} = \arg \min_g \|(f * g) - \Delta T\|_2^2 + \lambda \left\| \frac{dg}{dt} \right\|_2^2 \quad 2.6$$

where λ the relative weight of the STgF derivative ($\lambda > 0$). Increasing this parameter enhances the smoothness of \hat{g} at the expense of the precision (goodness of fit). Using Eq. 2.3 in Eq. 2.6, it is possible to explicit the calculation of the objective function $J(\hat{g})$, as show in Eq. 2.8, where the derivative of the STgF is expressed by a matrix multiplication ($D\hat{g}$). The solution is a direct computation of the STgF as shown in Eq. 2.9. Matrix D of size (n-1) by n is the first-order finite difference matrix, as described on Eq. 2.7:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad 2.7$$

$$J(\hat{g}) = (F\hat{g} - \Delta T)^T (F\hat{g} - \Delta T) + \lambda (D\hat{g})^T (D\hat{g}) \quad 2.8$$

To minimize the least squares of the previous equation, the partial derivative of J with respect to \hat{g} should equal 0 at the minimum, leading to Eq. 2.9:

$$\hat{g} = (F^T F + \lambda D^T D)^{-1} F^T \Delta T \quad 2.9$$

which is a regularized weighted deconvolution algorithm that extracts a STgF.

Since this algorithm uses experimental data, the results are affected by noise on the recording variables (Witte, 2013). To limit noise impact, a low-pass filter can be applied since recording error are of high frequency. The moving average or the Gaussian window moving average are both excellent filters for time-domain data set (Smith, 1999).

The methodology to obtain a STgF with a deconvolution algorithm is summarized below:

1. Retrieve the heat flux Q , the circulating flow V , the initial ground temperature T_0 and the outlet GHE temperature T_{out} from a TRT.
2. Since V is on the denominator of Eq. 2.2, change every 0 value for a small value close to the machine precision.
3. Calculate the temperature variation $T_{out} - T_0$.
4. Apply either a moving average or a Gaussian window moving average on $(T_{out} - T_0)$ and \dot{Q} .
5. Calculate the incremental heat load function f with Eq. 2.2.
6. Construct the Toeplitz matrix F and sparse matrix D .
7. Set the lambda factor to 0.5 at first and adjust its value subsequently according to the smoothness of the deconvolve STgF.
8. Solve the Eq. 2.9.

3. Results

The deconvolution algorithm was applied to different numerical and experimental data sets on both closed loop and standing column well systems. Here, only the results of a real TRT performed on a standing column well are deconvolved to obtain the STgF. Fig. 1 shows the experimental data extracted from the TRT. The undisturbed ground temperature T_0 is equal to 12.35 °C and retrieved with a recirculation test prior to the TRT.

Fig. 1 – Experimental data ($\dot{Q}, \dot{V}, T_{in}, T_{out}$) for a TRT performed on a standing column well. The value T_0 is equal to 12.35 °C (Beaudry et al., 2019).

After solving Eq. 2.9, the STgF obtained can be convolved with Eq. 2.1 and the convolved temperature variations is compared with the initial temperature variations to assess the performance of the method (Marcotte & Pasquier, 2008; Pasquier & Marcotte, 2013).

Fig. 2 shows the results of the deconvolution and the subsequent convolution to obtain the original temperature variations retrieve from the TRT. Table 1 shows the *root-mean-square-error* (RMSE) between the convolved temperature variations and the reference temperature variation obtained with the TRT.

Table 1. RMSE between convolve and reference temperature variations. Convolution uses the deconvolved STgF.

Approach	RMSE [°C]
1. Measured	0.009
2. Moving average	0.011
3. Gaussian moving average	0.006

4. Discussion

The STgF on Fig. 2 shows satisfactory results regarding the robustness of the proposed deconvolution method. All the curves are close to each other, with minimal deviation according to the different approaches used. This last statement is also confirmed when the STgF are compared to the reference temperature variation as is shown in Table 1. Usually, the moving average filter helps lowering the RMSE in the time domain since high frequency are attenuated, but on this test case, only the Gaussian

Fig. 2 –Deconvolved STgF (top), convolved and reference temperature variation $T_{out} - T_0$ (bottom). Forms are present to differentiate the curves.

moving average allows greater precision on the reconstructed STgFs.

The algorithm induces some error toward the end of the STgF. Since the definition of a transfer function is the response of a system under a unit impulse at initial time, two main properties can be inferred: (1) the transfer function must be strictly positive and (2) the derivative of the transfer function should always be greater than 0. This comes with the realistic assumption that the transfer function should be smooth and continuous. Although the STgF shown have good form, the smoothness and positive derivative are not respected toward the end, especially at the start of the restitution phase.

The parameter λ can be changed to enhance the smoothing effect, but at the cost of the precision on the reconstructed STgF. Tests indicate that optimal values are between 0.5 and 1. The lowest RMSE will be obtained with $\lambda = 0$, since it cancels the regularization. Hence, it is apparent to resolving the Eq. 2.3 directly with Eq. 2.5.

It is worth pointing out that the algorithm was applied successfully on a variety of other TRT data set with various effects as power interruption and different GHE type.

The precedent deconvolution algorithm is implemented on the software package MATLAB (MATLAB, 2020). The computation of Eq. 2.9 is heavy for long TRT since the construction of matrix F requires high Random-access memory (RAM) usage. For example, on an array of length $n = 25\,000$, the RAM can go as high as 23 Gb of and computing time is around 3.5 minutes. The computation cost is proportional to n^2 .

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a regularized weighted deconvolution algorithm to obtain the STgF from the experimental data set of a TRT. The proposed algorithm shows good promise in retrieving the STgF without model error since no analytical or numerical model is applied to reconstruct the STgF.

Future works should aim at stabilizing the STgF reconstruction, improve efficiency and provide more validation against various experimental test cases.

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PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF A SOLAR ASSISTED GROUND SOURCE HEAT PUMP SYSTEM FOR NUNAVIK

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Keywords: Solar Assisted Ground Source Heat Pump; Design parameters; Ground thermal depletion; TRNSYS simulation; Subarctic climate

Abstract

In recent years, studies have investigated the ability of ground source heat pumps to provide heat for remote and off-grid northern communities. Solar assistance appears as a solution to avoid their performance degradation over time due to thermal depletion of the ground. Integration of solar energy into the energy balance of these communities calls for a long-term energy storage strategy. Long-term ground thermal storage is a promising approach, but there is a gap of knowledge on the application of this strategy in the arctic or subarctic context.

This study aims to model a solar assisted ground source heat pump, which relies on photovoltaic panels and vertical boreholes. It provides heat for a research facility located in Whapmagoostui-Kuujuarapik, in Nunavik (Quebec). We used the heat load data from one of the buildings of this facility as the heat demand that must be partially satisfied by the heat pump system. The energy balance, and the ground thermal depletion affecting the performance of the system, are investigated, based on TRNSYS simulations. The results show that the solar assisted ground source heat pump can provide 36.8% of the building heat load, over 10 years of operation.

1. Introduction

The Centre d'études nordiques (CEN) considers building a seasonal heat storage system for its research facility in Nunavik. This can be achieved with Ground Source Heat Pumps (GSHP), but there is currently a lack of experience and uncertainties associated with the use of this technology in cold climates (Meyer et al., 2011, Garber-Slaght et al., 2014, Giordano et al., 2018, Giordano et al., 2019, Gunawan et al., 2020). One concern is the ground temperature depletion over years of operation, and the resulting low heat carrier fluid temperature that could prevent the heat pump from working, the lower limit being around -6.7°C (Belzile et al., 2017). The present study focuses on a potential design of a Solar Assisted Ground Source Heat Pump (SAGSHP), for the subarctic

conditions. The design considers long-term thermal storage in the ground. The objective is to assess its performance under a continuous operation strategy, and to evaluate the ground temperature depletion over an operation of 10 years.

2. Methods

2.1 – Configuration description

An energy model of the case study building was developed on TRNSYS and was calibrated based on the actual energy bills. This software is mainly used for building and renewable energy simulation. According to the simulations of the calibrated model, the heating consumption is ~ 100 GJ/year. Figure 1 gives the yearly profile of the building heating load. Currently, this load is fully satisfied by a fuel oil furnace. This profile is taken as the load to satisfy in the present study, assuming that a portion of it could be supplied by the SAGSHP system in parallel to the furnace.

Fig.1. Variations of the building heating load during a typical year

Figure 2 shows the configuration of the SAGSHP under study. In the Nunavik conditions, photovoltaic energy is deemed preferable than thermal solar energy to lower maintenance and transportation costs of components. Consequently, the TRNSYS model of this system includes a 0.8 m^3 water storage tank heated by 8 kW photovoltaic panels (PV), a boreholes field that contains two 100 m-deep U-pipes ground heat exchangers (GHE), and one heat pump with a nominal heating capacity of 2.97 kW.

Fig.2. Components of the SAGSHP

One pump and four controlled flow diverters and mixers allow the circulation of the fluid as seen in Figure 2. In the present study, we assumed that the heat pump provided a fix amount of heat during 185 days of the year while the furnace followed the fluctuation of the load. The furnace also satisfied the heating load during the remaining 180 days of the year when needed (i.e. during summer). The configuration of the SAGSHP allows three main operation modes:

Mode 1 occurs when the heat pump provides heat to the house. The fluid circulates in the water tank before entering the GHE and the heat pump (v4 and v1 opened, v2 and v3 closed). Heat is extracted from the ground. In this case, solar energy is supposed to overcome the heat losses through the tank wall and raise the fluid temperature in the tank.

Mode 2 increases the ground temperature to prevent thermal depletion. The water tank, assisted by the PV panels, delivers heat into the storage volume (v1 and v3 opened, v2 and v4 closed). In last resort, the fluid will stop circulating if the tank is unable to raise the fluid temperature. Despite the injection of heat, the borefield temperature could remain lower than the ground undisturbed temperature. In this case, the heat of the surrounding ground would also be transferred by conduction to the storage volume. Heat transfer by convection due to ground water flow is not considered in this present model.

Mode 3 provides the house with heating without using the solar energy. It replaces Mode 1 when the tank is unable to raise the fluid temperature (v2 and v4 opened, v1 and v3 closed). The heat is only extracted from the ground.

2.2 – Design parameters and operation strategy

Four main design parameters are identified: the number of boreholes, their spacing, their depth, and the rated photovoltaic power. This paper studies one combination

of these parameters, under a continuous operation strategy, which is detailed in Table 1. The features of the photovoltaic panels and the water source heat pump come from constructor catalogs.

Table 1. Main parameters for TRNSYS simulation

Item		Unit	Value
Ground heat exchangers	boreholes number	-	2
	boreholes spacing	m	10
	boreholes depth	m	100
	boreholes diameter	m	0.24
	u-pipe inside diameter	m	0.025
	u-pipe outside diameter	m	0.032
	fill thermal conductivity	W/(m.K)	1.5
	pipe thermal conductivity	W/(m.K)	0.5
Ground (unconsolidated sediments, unsaturated)	thermal conductivity	W/(m.K)	1.3
	thermal capacity	kJ/(m ³ .K)	1,750
	initial temperature	°C	2.0
Heat carrier fluid (ethylene-glycol-water mixture, 35% in mass)	density	kg/(m ³)	1048.5
	thermal capacity	kJ/(kg.K)	3.547
	mass flow rate	kg/s	0.5
Photovoltaic panels (two arrays, azimuths 0° and 180°)	rated power	W	8,000
	array slope	degrees	18
	efficiency	%	5.0
	single unit area	m ²	1.48
	number of units	-	32
Water tank	volume	m ³	0.8
	heat loss coefficient	W/(m ² .K)	0.33
Heat pump	rated heating capacity	W	2,970
	rated COP	-	4.1

The simulation is carried over a period of 10 years, with a time step of 10 minutes. The continuous operation strategy consists in providing the house with constant heat for 185 days through Modes 1 and 3, and injecting heat in the storage volume through Mode 2 during the remaining 180 days of the year. In this case, the extraction occurs during the coldest period of the year, while the injection occurs during the warmest period. From September 17th to March 21st of the next year, Modes 1 and Modes 3 were used alternatively, depending on the ability of the tank to raise the fluid temperature, and Mode 2 triggered from March 21st to September 17th.

Considering a heat pump working during 185 days with a heating rate of 2,970 W, the continuous operation strategy can theoretically provide the house with maximum 47.5% of its yearly heat load.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 3 reports the energy balance of the SAGSHP over a 10-year operation, during the building heating periods (extraction periods) and during the thermal recovery of the borefield (injection periods). It gives the relation between the energy provided to the building, the energy provided by the PV, the thermal depletion of the borefield, and the heat exchanges between the borefield and its environment – the surrounding ground and the atmosphere. These exchanges are given by E loss top, E loss side and E loss bottom, which are the heat losses through the surfaces of the volume containing the borefield, at the top, the side and the bottom. A negative value means that heat is transferred from the environment to the borefield, and vice versa. The thermal depletion and the thermal recovery of the borefield are given by E change borefield. A negative value means that the borefield temperature decreases, and a positive value means that it increases.

Fig.3. Sankey diagram of the energy balance of the SAGSHP for a 10-year operation – energy in [GJ]

According to Figure 3, during extraction and injection periods, E loss side and E loss bottom are negative, meaning that the borefield receives heat from the surrounding ground. On the contrary, the sign of the heat loss through the top surface (E loss top) means that heat is transferred to the atmosphere during the extraction periods, and that heat flow occurs in the opposite direction during the injection periods.

The energy provided by the water tank to the fluid is the energy provided by the PV (E elec PV) minus the heat losses (E loss water tank), minus the energy change of the tank (E change water tank). The thermal recovery of the

borefield occurs during the injection periods (positive E change borefield) and comes from two contributions: the water tank assistance and the heat exchanges between the environment and the borefield (negative E loss top, E loss side and E loss bottom). During the extraction periods, E from fluid to ground is negative, meaning that the borefield provides the HP with heat. In this case, the heat loss to the atmosphere (positive E loss top), and the heat extraction, cause the thermal depletion of the borefield and the heat transfer from the surrounding ground to the borefield (negative E loss side and E loss bottom). The difference between the borefield thermal depletion during the extraction periods, and the borefield thermal recovery during the injection periods, gives the borefield thermal depletion over 10 years (E change borefield NET). When looking at the net energy balance, including extraction and injection periods, the energy extracted by the heat pump comes from three main contributions: the net heat exchanges between the storage volume and its environment represents 26% of the heat extracted. The net borefield thermal depletion represents 6%, and the short-term storage tank provides the remaining 68%.

The borefield thermal depletion and the resulting decrease of the heat carrier fluid temperature over years are among the main concerns with ground source heat pumps. Figure 4 shows the change of the borefield temperature over its operation, the temperature of the fluid entering the GHE and the temperature of the fluid exiting the GHE. The alternance between injection and extraction periods can be seen. The GHE raises the fluid temperature during extraction periods, causing the decrease of the borefield temperature. On the contrary, the borefield receives heat from the fluid during the injection periods ($T_{in\ GHE} > T_{out\ GHE}$), thanks to the water tank assistance. As Figure 3 shows, the increase of the mean borefield temperature also occurs thanks to the heat exchanges with the environment (E loss top, E loss side and E loss bottom).

Fig.4. Mean borefield temperature, mean water tank temperature, and heat carrier fluid temperature entering and exiting the GHE, during a 10-year operation – daily averages

Fig.5. Mean borefield temperature and mean heat carrier fluid temperature exiting the GHE, during a 10-year operation – daily averages

Fig.6. Variations of COP during a 10-year operation – daily averages

On Figure 4, the profile of the mean water tank temperature explains the use of Mode 3. The photovoltaic production being insufficient during a part of the extraction periods, the water tank temperature falls below the circulating fluid temperature, calling for short-circuiting the water tank. It is worth to be noted that during extraction periods, the fluid exiting the GHE enters the heat pump. Its minimum temperature reaches -3.1°C and the minimum temperature of the fluid exiting the heat pump reaches -4.2°C , after an operation of 10 years. Both temperatures are higher than the lower limit fluid temperature for the selected HP, around -6.7°C . Figures 4 and 5 show that the borefield temperature remains stable during the 10-year operation and suggest that the solar assistance reduces the fluid and ground temperature depletion slightly, as it is already limited without solar assistance. Figure 6 emphasizes this limited improvement. The mean COP reaches 3.45 and the mean heating capacity reaches 2,877 W with solar assistance. In comparison, they respectively reach 3.36 and 2,784 W, without. As a result, the heat provided to the building, E to building, during an operation of 10 years, represents 46.0 % of the heat load on the same period, in presence of a solar assistance, while it provides 44.5 %, without solar assistance.

4. Conclusion

The results show that the SAGSHP design under study can provide the building with 46.0 % of its heat load, on average, during a 10-year operation. According to the net energy balance, 26% of the heat provided to the heat pump come from net exchanges between the borefield and its environment. The water tank provides 68% of this heat, while the net borefield thermal depletion provides the remaining 6%. This low ground thermal depletion allows the ground and fluid temperature, and the system performances, to remain stable over years of operation. However, the solar assistance contribution results in few improvements of the system performances. The effects of solar assistance on the boreholes required length should be investigated for higher extraction rates.

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Sustainability of thermal energy of geothermal systems by increasing the use of groundwater

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Keywords: Geothermal, groundwater, fracture, aquifer, numerical model

Abstract

Geothermal energy has the potential to significantly contribute to heating and cooling of industrial and resident buildings. Groundwater from the Upper Carbonate aquifer can be extensively used as an open loop source of heating and cooling purposes in Winnipeg, Canada. The objectives of this research were to increase the sustainability of a geothermal system by increasing the use of available groundwater and to determine the influence of fractures on groundwater temperature during open loop geothermal cycles. A numerical 3D model based on a discrete fracture network (DFN) was developed to determine conductive and convective heat transport. Twelve scenarios were considered differing in terms of flow rate (0.0076 m³/s to 0.030 m³/s), and the temperature changed by the heat pump and simulation time (1 to 10 years). The results were compared to a modeling attempt using an equivalent porous media instead of the DFN. The presence of fractures had a substantial influence on the change in groundwater temperature in terms of summer cooling but was limited in the case of winter heating. The results suggest that developing a model with DFN and determining its influence of change in temperature for a longer period is advisable for geothermal systems in fractured rocks that need to be energy balanced by summer cooling.

1. Introduction

Understanding the concept of groundwater flow and heat transport is important in assessing the sustainability of groundwater supplies and geothermal energy use in the area. Issues concerning the sustainability of groundwater resources due to climate change need to be addressed. Temperature measurements provide valuable insights to solve such concerns related to groundwater flow systems (Ferguson and Woodbury 2005). Heat exchange with the ground can be performed by different types of ground source energy (GSE) systems. It includes closed loop and open loop systems. This research mainly focuses on open loop systems in shallow geothermal systems in Winnipeg, Canada. The objective of this project is to evaluate the sustainability of thermal energy of the geothermal system

of an industrial facility in Winnipeg by increasing the use of available groundwater.

The project aims to supply and return around 4900 – 6540 m³/day for geothermal heating and cooling using the Friesen Drillers facility’s three existing supply wells and two return wells and also test the influence of fractures during those geothermal cycles.

2. Methods

The industrial site for this project specifically has 5 working wells as shown in Fig 1. The distance of the wells from an arbitrary centre was provided by the facility.

Fig 1: The exact locations of supply and return wells considered for the study
Return wells (orange) where the heated or cooled water is injected
Supply wells (blue) where the groundwater is pumped

The wells in the study area were completed in the carbonate aquifer and penetrated the full thickness of the aquifer. Table 1 shows each layer in order below the surface and Fig 2 shows the 3D model of lithology of all layers beneath the earth’s surface at the study area. The water levels and the discharge rates of the wells (both supply and return) were measured using a calibrated flow meter and an automatic depth sounder. The aquifer characteristics of the aquifer in the study area were determined using the logs containing the duration of pumping and recovery along with the calculated drawdown.

AQTESOLV software was used for the interpretation of aquifer tests. The hydraulic properties of the aquifer were determined using Baker’s solution (Baker 1988). The difference between the initial groundwater temperature in the supply well and the temperature when the water is injected into the return well is the amount of energy that is being utilized by the geothermal system for heating and cooling.

Fig 2: Lithology of the layers beneath the earth’s surface at study area and each depth is mentioned in Table 1

Table 1. Depths of each lithology layer at the study area.

Layer below surface	Depth below surface (m)
Surface	0.00
Clay	15.24
Till	23.16
Sand and Gravel	26.21
Limestone	46.00
Bedrock	76.20

Two pumping rates were considered to differentiate the change in temperature over the years and to determine the sustainability as required by the facility. The pumps were operated at maximum capacity throughout the day during winter months (November – March) for winter heating. For the rest of the months, when the buildings need to be cooled, the pumps operated at one fifth of the maximum capacity. **Table 2** shows the pumping rates and the assumed temperature in the return wells for summer cooling and winter heating for required durations. The initial temperature and assumptions of ΔT were obtained from (Ferguson and Woodbury 2004). The pumping rates for summer cooling and winter heating were considered to be constant for this study.

Table 2: Pumping rates and temperatures in return wells

Type	Duration	Initial pumping rate (m ³ /s)	Increased pumping rate (m ³ /s)	Initial ground water temperature (°C)	Temperature in return well ($\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$)	Temperature in return well ($\Delta T = 5^\circ\text{C}$)
Summer cooling	May – Sep	7.6×10^{-3}	0.03	8.5	10.5	13.5
	Oct-Apr	1.5×10^{-3}	6×10^{-3}			
Winter heating	Nov – Mar	7.6×10^{-3}	0.03	8.5	6.5	3.5
	Oct-Apr	1.5×10^{-3}	6×10^{-3}			

This study used the numerical software FEFLOW to stimulate heat transport in groundwater. Shape files of the domain area and the wells were imported into the FEFLOW. The built-in grid builder with 4000 proposed elements per slice was used for the mesh. 6 slices were utilized since the study area had 5 layers beneath the surface. Constant head, well and temperature were considered as boundary conditions (BC). Since the well boundary condition had different pumping rates, a time series with constant time steps were added. The known temperature BC helps in fixing the undisturbed ground temperature around a model for the local influence of a ground-source heat exchanger.

To determine the influence of fracture in heat transport, one 1D discrete feature based on the shortest node path between the pumping and return wells was considered (**Fig 3**). This was the only fracture present at the study area and confirmed from the well reports of Friesen Drillers. The fracture formed an arbitrary connection of several nodes in the mesh. It connects from one return well to a supply well horizontally at 26 m below the surface. The fracture is placed in slice 3.

Fig 3: Slice view of the fracture placed in the mesh.

In addition to the boundary conditions and model parametrization, initial conditions were necessary to run the model. This project emphasized the use of heat transport parameters such as thermal conductivity and heat capacity. Best fit values after referring multiple literatures were considered for this project. The values for the DFN were taken from Graf and Therrien (2005). Twelve scenarios were considered to show the sustainability of the geothermal installation as shown in **Table 3**. Multiple scenarios assist to determine various outcomes for different pumping rates, the difference in temperatures and simulation times. Three varying simulation times (1, 5 and 10 years) with automatic time step control were considered to determine how the water temperature changes over years. The hydraulic head and the temperature were overridden to zero and 8.5°C respectively. An observation point was kept at a distance of 5 m from the return well to monitor the change in temperature over time.

Table 3: Twelve scenarios considered to show sustainability

Scenario No.	Type	ΔT (°C)	Duration (years)	Influence of fracture	Pumping rate (m ³ /s)
S1	Summer cooling	5	1, 5 & 10	No	7.6*10 ⁻³
S2				Yes	
S3	Winter heating	2	1, 5 & 10	No	0.03
S4				Yes	
S5	Summer cooling	2	1, 5 & 10	No	0.03
S6				Yes	
S7	Winter heating	5	1, 5 & 10	No	0.03
S8				Yes	
S9	Summer cooling	5	1, 5 & 10	No	0.03
S10				Yes	
S11	Winter heating	2	1, 5 & 10	No	0.03
S12				Yes	

3. Results

The results of scenarios 5 to 8 (Table 4) were examined by the change in temperature for summer cooling and winter heating at observation point located 5 m away from the return well for simulation times 1, 5 and 10 years for increased discharge of 0.03 m³/s, $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, with and without the influence of fractures measured at 3rd slice.

Table 4: Comparison of final change in temperature (2°C) of flow rate 0.03 m³/s at the end of simulation times

	Change in temperature (°C) for 1 year		Change in temperature (°C) for 5 years		Change in temperature (°C) for 10 years	
	With fracture	Without fracture	With fracture	Without fracture	With fracture	Without fracture
Summer cooling	8.90	9.05	9.18	9.30	9.30	9.42
Winter heating	8.25	8.10	7.95	7.82	7.75	7.70

For scenarios 5 & 6, the difference in temperature with and without DFN ranges from only 0.1 - 0.2°C (Fig 4 and 5). Fig 4 and 5 are a sample results of S5 & S6 but simulation and graphs for other scenarios (summer cooling and winter heating for 1 year) were performed and results are shown in Table 4. The same difference in temperature range was maintained till the end of simulation times.

Fig.4: Summer cooling for 5 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away form well

Fig.5: Summer cooling for 10 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away form well

Scenarios 7 & 8 for winter heating (Fig 6 and 7) showed that the temperature difference is much smaller than summer cooling temperatures. The temperature change varied from 0.05 – 0.1°C. It showed a minimal influence of fracture in winter heating if the temperature difference was 2°C, even when the pumping rates were high.

Fig.6: Winter heating for 5 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away form well

Fig.7: Winter heating for 10 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away form well

Scenario 9 to 12 (Table 5) shows the results of one extreme possible condition (maximum temperature difference of 5°C at maximum flow rate of 0.03 m³/s) which were considered to determine the sustainability.

Table 5: Final temperature if return well is allowed to change groundwater temperature by 5°C and flow rate 0.03 m³/s

	1 year of operation (°C)		5 years of operation (°C)		10 years of operation (°C)	
	With fracture	Without fracture	With fracture	Without fracture	With fracture	Without fracture
Summer cooling	9.47	9.85	10.21	10.50	10.34	10.52
Winter heating	7.70	7.55	6.90	6.85	6.60	6.40

The results of summer cooling with increased flow rates (Fig 8 and 9) showed similar traits to summer cooling with minimal flow rates. The temperature difference ranged from 0.2 to 0.4°C with the presence of a fracture. Hence, for summer cooling irrespective of the discharge rate, the influence of fracture was considerable. While for winter heating, the temperature change was very minimal with the presence of fractures (Fig 10 and 11). Summer cooling and winter heating for 1 year with increased flow rate were performed and results are shown in Table 1.

Fig.8: Summer cooling for 5 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 5^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away from well

Fig.9: Summer cooling for 10 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 5^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away from well

Fig.10: Winter heating for 5 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 5^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away from well

Fig.11: Winter heating for 10 years with and without fracture at $\Delta T = 5^\circ\text{C}$, 5 m away from well

4. Discussion

Summer cooling for all the scenarios showed a difference in temperature if fractures were present in the aquifer. Fractures influenced the change of temperature over a period of 40 - 50 years. The temperature of the groundwater was slightly higher at the observation point 5 m away from the return well, when compared to simulation without fractures. The reason is that that warm water flows to the supply well through the fracture acting as a preferential flow path. If the injected water reaches the supply wells, then the efficiency of the geothermal system decreases due to the lower temperature difference. Additionally, because of the temperature difference, the temperature of the groundwater will no longer be 8.5°C. Hence, the presence of fracture delays the possibility of change in temperature to reach the supply well by few years. The temperature at the observation point increased by approximately 1°C in 10 years. This is the same in the case of both presence and absence of fracture. But the only difference is that the increase in temperature at the end of 1st year with a fracture is less than the rise in temperature without a fracture. The increase in temperature was similar in the case of increased flow rate. The temperature at the observation point with increased flow rate had 9.85°C at the end of the 1st year and increased to only 10.52°C, which is similar to a low flow rate. If the same flow rate is continued, the temperature at the nearest supply well which is approximately 135 m from the injection well will have an increase in groundwater temperature by 1°C after 270 years. However, the constant temperature of groundwater will be changed long before and the geothermal system will have less efficiency. If a supply well is present close to the return wells in the presence of a fractured aquifer, then the efficiency of the geothermal system can be extended. In the case of winter heating, there was no significance difference in temperature at a particular distance from the return well. In most of the scenarios of winter heating, there was no difference in temperature in the 1st year, irrespective of the fracture's presence. This was seen in all the graphs of winter cooling where there is an overlap of temperature with and

without the influence of fracture. A slight change in temperature within the range of 0.05 to 0.1°C was observed if a fracture was present. However, while considering the temperature change in the aquifer over 10 years, the temperature at the end of the 1st year is observed to be 7.5°C and it decreased to 6.5°C over 10 years. It decreased by 1°C in the case of low flow rates. Similarly, if the flow rate was increased the difference in the decrease in temperature is approximately the same. It decreases by 1.3°C. Hence, the flow rate can be increased for both summer cooling and winter heating purposes for the industrial facility. The difference between summer cooling and winter heating is that the presence of DFN influences the change in temperature for summer cooling but does not have a considerable impact on winter heating.

5. Conclusions

The simulations in this study indicate that the requirement proposed by the Friesen drillers' facility is accomplished. Friesen Drillers' wanted to increase the use of groundwater and to increase the sustainability of their geothermal systems. Initially their groundwater flow rates were only 0.0076m³/s and aimed to increase it. This study proved that they can increase their groundwater usage and still have sustainable geothermal systems over a longer period. It was verified that the presence of fracture has the influence of change in groundwater temperature to a significant extent in terms of summer cooling. However, the impact of the presence of fractures is limited in the case of winter heating. It can be advised that they can increase the flow rate and still have the same efficiency for a long period.

Recommendations and future work:

Identifying the presence of fractures in the aquifer and drilling return wells to increase the sustainability of the geothermal systems.

Model with multiple fracture networks in the layers and determine the influence of change in temperature for a long period.

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Harnessing heat from sedimentary basins to heat buildings in cold climates: A modeling study.

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Abstract

Geothermal heat is a promising alternative to heat buildings. Here, heat extraction from sedimentary basins at 1-2 km depth was numerically simulated considering two types of systems: well doublet and deep borehole heat exchangers (DBHE). A sensitivity analysis was conducted to test 1) the impact of the most influential properties and 2) boundary conditions, which can both spatially vary in sedimentary basins. For the well doublet, hydraulic conductivity (K), flow rate and distance between production and injection wells were varied. For DBHEs, thermal conductivity of rocks and the Earth heat flux were varied.

Simulation results showed that a 1200 m deep geothermal doublet in a 400 m thick aquifer can produce more energy than a 1500 m DBHE. Indeed, up to 1300 GWh can be produced using a 1200 m doublet system over a 30-year period when $K \geq 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ or 245 GWh if $K = 10^{-8} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ against 24-29 GWh using a 1500 m DBHE for the same geothermal heat flux condition. Future work will consider more scenarios to refine the comparison between these two system types.

1. Introduction

In Canada, space and water heating represented 81% of residential and 62% of commercial and institutional buildings energy consumption in 2017 (Natural Resource Canada (NRCAN), 2020). Geothermal energy can help fulfill this heat demand. It is a local and renewable energy directly present as geothermal heat and is available regardless of weather conditions (Kagel, Bates, & Gawell, 2005).

The objective of this study is to assess the potential of harnessing heat at 1-2 km depth in sedimentary basins to heat buildings in cold climates. Geothermal well doublets are typically envisioned where aquifer units are present, while deep borehole heat exchangers (DBHE) are generally intended for less permeable units. However, the

performance of both systems has rarely been compared for similar hydrogeological conditions.

2. Methods

A simple geological model composed of three distinct homogeneous units, presented in Figure 1, was used for this preliminary study.

Figure 1: Geological setting and geothermal systems considered in this study. Red corresponds to "hot" water while blue corresponds to "cold" water. The light blue line corresponds to the water table.

Values for the base case scenario are presented in Figure 1. The deep aquifer layer (800-1200 m) was considered made of either limestone, dolostone, sandstone or a mix of the three. The aquitard units are considered made of siltstone and shale. When the hydraulic conductivity (K) is below 10^{-9} m/s , the bedrock is considered nearly impermeable, and well doublets are not operational without permeability enhancement (not considered in this study). Therefore, K for the deep aquifer was selected to range from 10^{-9} m s^{-1} to $6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (see Figure 2). The selected thermal conductivity (λ) of this aquifer ranged between $2.0 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and $4.8 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and for the aquitards, between 1.5 and $3.0 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

The performance of the different geothermal systems was evaluated using 2D well doublet and 3D BHE models,

developed with the finite element software FEFLOW (DHI).

Figure 2: Typical K and thermal conductivity values for sedimentary rocks. (AQTESOLV; Gascuel, Bédard, Comeau, Raymond, & Malo, (2020) and all references therein)

2.1 Geothermal well doublet

The impact of spacing between injection and production wells, and of fluid flow were studied using 30-year simulations for different hydraulic conductivities of the deep aquifer. The sensitivity to thermal conductivity with respect to energy produced from a well doublet was not verified. However, it is expected to be smaller than that of K.

For these preliminary simulations, 2D models were developed assuming steady pumping and injection rates, a fixed injection temperature of 0°C, and a uniform initial temperature of nearly 30°C. A constant and equal hydraulic head and temperature were imposed on opposite lateral boundaries (no regional groundwater flow).

The thermal energy produced and the energy consumed to operate the pump of the systems were calculated and compared. The skin effect was taken into account assuming that for wells with a diameter of 156 mm, the skin zone would have a radius of 1 m and a permeability of $4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2$ (finite thickness skin method in Bourdarot and Balvet (1998)). Plate heat exchangers, which are required to avoid damage to the heat pump in open loop systems, were assumed to have an efficiency of 90%.

2.2 Deep borehole heat exchangers

The performance of a 1500 m coaxial DBHE was simulated for various rock thermal conductivity and heat fluxes (40 mW m^{-2} to 85 mW m^{-2}).

This DBHE was assumed to be installed in a 220 mm diameter borehole, with a 219 mm steel outer pipe presumed to be directly inserted in the borehole. The inner pipe is made of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) with thermal conductivity $\sim 0.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, such as those already used in DBHEs in China (Z. Wang et al., 2017). Their diameter and thickness are 114 mm and 8 mm, respectively.

3D models were developed assuming a constant surface temperature of 8°C and bottom heat flux. A constant and equal hydraulic head was assigned to lateral boundaries. Fluid flow was solved in steady state, with transient heat transfer.

3. Results

3.1 Geothermal well doublet

The simulated geothermal well doublet system can produce up to a maximum net energy of 1392 GWh in 30 years with $K=6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $D=2000 \text{ m}$ (Figure 3). For $K=10^{-9} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the energy required to run the pumps exceeds the thermal energy extracted, even with a low fluid flow of $0.01 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a 600 m spacing between wells. Therefore, the minimum K considered here was $K=10^{-8} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

Figure 3: Comparison of net energy produced by geothermal doublets for the selected range of K and the two distances between wells (D). The net energy corresponds to the produced energy subtracted by that needed to operate the pumps.

Figure 4: Comparison of hydraulic heads in the pumping well for the selected range of aquifer hydraulic conductivity (K) and the two distances between wells (D). The straight blue line represents the top of the aquifer.

The thermal energy produced and the pumping power required to operate a well doublet both increase with fluid flow. Thermal output is independent of aquifer K when

flow rates are imposed; however, the required pumping power increases when K decreases due to the larger drawdown (Figure 4). With a smaller spacing between wells, the required pumping power decreases, but this is only significant for aquifers with low K ($<10^{-7}$ m/s) and high fluid flow (Figure 3). The decline in energy output observed in Figure 3 for $D=600$ m compared to $D=2000$ m with fluid flows higher than 0.11 m³ s⁻¹ and $K \geq 10^{-7}$ m s⁻¹ is due to a thermal short-circuiting occurring during the simulation period.

Drawdown, is a limiting technical factor (Figure 4). For every permeability scenario, there is a maximum operating fluid flow to avoid dewatering of the aquifer over the 30-year period. It is lower than that determined from an energy production perspective for low K .

3.2 Deep borehole heat exchangers

Figure 5: Comparison of DBHE performances with respect to the geothermal heat flux (A) and thermal conductivity of the bedrock (B). The energy produced corresponds to the heat production over 30 years of constant operation minus the energy needed to operate the pump over that same period.

The performance of the DBHE is most sensitive to the geothermal heat flux. Figure 5A shows that 22 to 35 GWh could be produced over 30 years. It controls the initial underground temperature, affecting the potential energy to be extracted by cooling the rock. The thermal

conductivity of the deep aquifer also has, to a lesser extent, an impact as between 24.6 and 29 GWh could be produced (Figure 5B). When it increases, the initial temperature of geological units decreases, but the DBHE can extract heat more efficiently from the aquifer and will thus produce more heat. When the thermal conductivity of the aquitard is changed, a double effect can be seen. On the one hand, an aquitard with low thermal conductivity has an insulating effect in the upper part of the model. The initial temperature is thus greater in the entire model. On the other hand, a larger aquitard thermal conductivity enables the DBHE system to extract heat more efficiently from the aquitard layers.

4. Discussion

Although the numerical simulations showed that well doublets can produce more energy than DBHEs, well doublets are, nonetheless, dependent upon the permeability of the bedrock. Deep aquifers are typically heterogeneous and this strongly impacts their K and, in turn, the performance of geothermal well doublets. In particular, the degree of interconnection of fractures between the two wells can affect the efficiency of these systems, as a poorly connected fracture network can lead to the use of few fractures (“preferential path”) by the fluid. In such cases, the heat extraction is far from optimal, as heat is extracted from a few fractures only (eg. Babaei & Nick, 2019; Crooijmans, Willems, Nick, & Bruhn, 2016; Liu, Pu, Zhao, & Liu, 2019; Vogt et al., 2013). Additionally, the time for thermal short-circuiting, after which a continuous loss of performance occurs, could differ significantly from the simulations presented here that considered the different units to be homogenous equivalent porous media. For these reasons, high uncertainty and risks are associated to the development of well doublet systems.

The performances of DBHEs could be improved by introducing a natural groundwater flow in the aquifer that would provide continuous recharge of heat from the flowing hot brine (Chiasson, Rees, & Spitler, 2000; Diao, Li, & Fang, 2004; H. Wang, Qi, Du, & Gu, 2009). However, only a weak hydraulic gradient is generally present in deep aquifers of sedimentary basins with a commonly flat topography. Performance could also be improved by using the DBHE only for part of the year, as the rock surrounding the DBHE would have more time to recover from heat conduction.

5. Conclusions

The thermal energy outputs of a 1200 m geothermal well doublet were investigated for different K values commonly encountered in sedimentary basins,

considering a 400 m thick deep aquifer. These results were compared to the thermal energy outputs of a 1500 m deep DBHE obtained using different thermal conductivity and heat flux values. The minimum K over which well doublets perform better than the DBHEs is between 10^{-8} and 10^{-9} m s^{-1} . Indeed, even in a poorly permeable aquifer ($K=10^{-8}$ m s^{-1}), a geothermal well doublet with a low fluid flow can still produce more energy over 30-year period than 2 DBHEs (245 GWh with a well spacing of 600 m against 51 GWh for 2 DBHEs). With a higher K , the efficiency of a geothermal well doublet increases rapidly.

Many hypotheses and simplifications were made for the simulations presented here. Next steps include the development of 3D models for geothermal doublet systems to take into account the effect of thermal recharge by the aquitard and possible well deviation. Their sensitivity to thermal conductivity and heat flux will also be examined. Also, the performance of both geothermal well doublets and DBHEs will be compared to fulfill a seasonally varying heat demand. Finally, the performance of these systems will be studied using models with increasing geological complexity to better represent conditions of the Bécancour area in the St. Lawrence Lowlands in Québec, Canada.

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DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS IN SUBARCTIC CLIMATE

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Keywords: Thermal energy storage system, Geothermal energy, Sensitivity analysis, Design, Cold climate

Abstract

Borehole thermal energy storage system (BTES) is a mature technology to provide heating needs of buildings. It can thus contribute to the transition to sustainable green energies in northern Canada. Its efficiency strongly depends on the design and the subsurface conditions in which it is implemented. This study presents a sensitivity analysis of the main parameters influencing BTES operating in the subsurface near freezing conditions. Numerical simulations were performed in FEFLOW to estimate the average heat pump coefficient of performance (COP) of 68 different scenarios of a BTES with 25 borehole heat exchangers (BHE). An initial scenario was constructed and the COP was averaged during heat extraction periods. Then, 17 parameters were varied at constant steps (10% and 30% of their initial value) and their averaged COP was compared to the base case scenario. Results highlight parameters that need to be accurately estimated and optimized in order to maximize BTES efficiency. Thermal power injection/extraction, surface/volume ratio, BHE spacing, BTES layout compared to local groundwater direction and subsurface thermal properties are the parameters with the highest influence on the operating temperature. BTES initial scenario averages a COP of 2.92 over 4 years of operation. Worst-case scenario shows a mean COP of 2.74, whereas best-case scenario averages a COP of 3.05. This leads to a 13 GJ (+5.3%) energy gain difference between the worst and the best-case scenario over ~5.6 years of operation of heat extraction.

1. Introduction

Northern communities in Canada rely on fossil fuel to supply heating loads of their buildings. Ground-source heat pumps (GSHP) seem to be an interesting solution (Gunawan et al., 2020; Belzile et al., 2017). They can supply base-load heating needs and reduce fuel oil consumption which is the principal energy source of those communities. However, GSHP range of operation is commonly limited by the temperature of the heat carrier

fluid such as $-6.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Belzile et al., 2016). An alternative to prevent low temperature operation is BTES, a technology combining low-enthalpy geothermal technology to other green renewable energies such as solar energy. Solar radiation is converted into heat and transferred to the ground. Heat is stored in the ground throughout summer (maximum solar radiation), and then extracted during winter (maximum building's heating load) to ensure operation of the heat pump within a reasonable temperature range. The study site is located near the *Centre d'Études Nordiques* (CEN) research station at Whapmagoostui-Kuujuarapik in northern Quebec. The accessibility of the facilities and heating load data of the building was a major reason to choose this site. The regional geology is composed of a low-permeable granitic bedrock, partially covered by unconsolidated sediments, where fractures govern groundwater flow within either a confined or an unconfined aquifer (Fortier et al., 2011). Designing a BTES can be laborious since there are numerous parameters affecting its performance. This study aims to assess the main parameters and their impact on a BTES's performance in a subarctic climate. Numerical simulations are used to calculate the COP of different scenarios.

2. Methods

Numerical modelling is an efficient calculation method to solve coupled heat transfer problems such as BTES operation under groundwater flow influence. Numerical models were thus developed in FEFLOW (Diersch, 2014) to simulate groundwater flow and heat transfer mechanisms of the studied granitic media near the CEN. The developed model distinguishes five input parameter categories: thermal and hydrogeological properties, boundary conditions (BC), BHE configuration, and heating power demand.

For this study, we considered a simplified conceptual model only made of granitic bedrock, the principal geological formation in the area. Eleven granitic outcrops were sampled near the CEN and analyzed for thermal property assessment at the Laboratoire Ouvert de

Géothermie (LOG) at INRS-ETE. Hydrogeological data from previous groundwater research studies in Whapmagoostui-Kuujuarapik were inventoried (GPR International inc., 2002). These data were used to simulate and calibrate a regional 3D groundwater flow numerical model in order to estimate the bedrock's hydraulic conductivity and the hydraulic gradient at the CEN. This numerical model was also used to define hydrogeological BC to the BTES numerical model. Heat transfer BC were determined according to data collected from previous field campaigns. Ground temperature data were recorded at 1 m and 2 m depth over the 2018-2019 period in unconsolidated sediments near the CEN. Air temperature data recorded at the CEN's meteorological station (CEN, 2017) were also collected. These temperature data were used to define the surface temperature BC at the top of the model from 152 to 304 days. Ground temperature shows the insulating effect of the snow cover. A -1 °C surface temperature was therefore assigned from 0 to 152 days and from 304 to 365 days in order to represent this effect (Fig.1a). Temperature profiles recorded in observation wells (< 120 m depth) in the vicinity of the CEN were used to define a constant temperature boundary at the bottom of the model.

The BTES is composed of 25 BHE spaced by 3 m forming a cubic storage volume of 1728 m³ (12 x 12 x 12 m), with 864 m² (12m x 12m x 6 sides) of exposed surfaces with a minimal surface/volume ratio (0.5 m⁻¹; Skarphagen et al., 2019). The initial BTES configuration was determined to obtain a reasonable thermal storage volume that keeps the heat carrier fluid temperature operating range above -6.7 °C to respect a lower operating threshold temperature typically available in commercial heat pumps.

Extracted energy yearly profile (Fig.1b) of a yearlong inhabited residential building at the CEN in Whapmagoostui-Kuujuarapik was estimated by the mechanical engineering team of Université Laval involved in this research project. Heating load was estimated with simulations in TRNSYS according to building plans and occupation, and then calibrated with the 2018-2019 diesel energy bills. Injected energy yearly profile was calculated according to the following elements: the recorded solar radiation data at the CEN's meteorological station from 2005 to 2016 (CEN, 2017); the maximum number of photovoltaic solar panels to be installed on the CEN's roofs (162 solar panels of 2 m²); a solar panel efficiency of 14% (standard crystalline silicon panel); a power loss of 5% due to dip and orientation of solar panels (https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/fr/); a hypothetical 10% heat loss due to tank storage/heat circulation.

The numerical model mesh of the initial scenario has 34 400 nodes, 63 745 prismatic triangular elements,

20 layers, 25 interconnected BHEs within 2 arrays (Fig.1a). The total borehole length was always equal to 300 m (12 m depth) even when the BHE spacing (parameter 1, Tab.1) and the surface/volume ratio (parameter 5, Tab.1) were varied (e.g. surface/volume ratio +10% = prismatic rectangle with edges of 6.99m x 20.61 m and a depth of 12 m). Nodal distance around BHE was defined according to Diersch et al. (2011), and the mesh was refined around the BTES. Time steps of 0.1 days were used for ~5.6 years (1955 days), in which there is heat injection from 120 to 274 days and no heat extraction from 274 to 485 days. We assume isotropic and homogeneous material, transient fluid flow /heat transfer and a fully confined aquifer for simplicity.

Fig. 1. a) Mesh construction and BC applied to BTES numerical model; b) energy yearly profile of the BTES.

Python scripts were also developed to process and simulate a heat pump when there is heat extraction from the BTES. The outlet temperature fluid of the arrays is retrieved at each time step and the COP is calculated according to technical details of an ecoGEO 1-9 kW heat pump (EcoForest, 2020). Inlet temperature of the arrays at the next time step is then calculated according to the COP. The entry point of the injected heat is at the BTES' upstream while heat extraction starts from the BTES' downstream (Fig.1a). Temperature at 6 m depth in the center of the BTES and 27 m out of the BTES' center is retrieved for each simulation (Fig.1a).

Parameters were varied one at a time by ±10% and ±30% of their initial scenario value to perform a sensitivity analysis. Each time a parameter was varied, the average COP of the four years of energy extraction simulation was estimated and then compared to the initial scenario.

Table 1 presents all parameters considered for the sensitivity analysis where 68 different scenarios were run. Worst and best-case scenarios were then simulated according to the values producing the lowest COP loss (worst-case scenario) or the greatest COP gain (best-case scenario) from the base case scenario. These two scenarios use the power extraction and injection values of the base case scenario in order to compare energy savings on the same basis. The selected value of each parameter for the worst/best-case is the same as its base case scenario value if there is no difference or no positive COP difference.

Table 1. Parameters values to perform the sensitivity analysis.

Category	Parameter	Base case scenario	Difference from initial scenario	
			±10 %	±30 %
(A) BTES configuration	(1) Distance between BHE (m)	3.00	±0.30	±0.90
	(2) Borehole diameter (mm)	152.40	±15.24	±45.72
	(3) Difference between BTES and hydraulic gradient direction (°)	0.00	±18.00	±54.00
	(4) Flow rate (m ³ s ⁻¹)	8.00·10 ⁻⁴	±0.80·10 ⁻⁴	±2.40·10 ⁻⁴
	(5) Ratio surface/volume	Ratio (m ⁻¹) Surface (m ²)	0.50 864.00	0.05 86.40
(B) Thermal property	(6) Borehole thermal resistance (m·K·W ⁻¹)	8.00·10 ⁻²	±0.80·10 ⁻²	±2.40·10 ⁻²
	(7) λ _{fluid} (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	0.48	±4.80·10 ⁻²	±14.40·10 ⁻²
	(8) ρC _{p, fluid} (MJ·m ⁻³ ·K ⁻¹)	3.80	±0.38	±1.14
	(9) λ (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	2.88	±0.29	±0.86
	(10) ρC _p (MJ·m ⁻³ ·K ⁻¹)	2.30	±0.23	±0.69
(C) Hydrogeological	(11) K (m·s ⁻¹)	5.80·10 ⁻⁷	±0.60·10 ⁻⁷	±1.80·10 ⁻⁷
	(12) S _v (m ⁻¹)	4.60·10 ⁻⁵	±0.50·10 ⁻⁵	±1.40·10 ⁻⁵
	(13) θ (-)	0.02·10 ⁰	±0.02·10 ⁻¹	±0.06·10 ⁻¹
(D) Boundary condition	(14) h (m)	1.50	±0.15	±0.45
	(15) Heat transfer rate (W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹)	20.00	±2.00	±6.00
	(16) Average power extraction (kW)	5.42	±0.54	±1.63
(E) Heat power	(17) Average power injection (kW)	-9.63	±0.96	±2.89

3. Results

Results for the initial scenario averaged a COP of 2.92 throughout 4 years, a maximum and minimum simulated heat carrier fluid temperature at the inlet heat pump of 18.16 °C and -2.52 °C, respectively. A maximum and minimum simulated temperature of 16.42 °C and -0.92 °C were recorded in the middle of the BTES at 6 m depth, respectively. A maximum and minimum simulated temperature of 4.18 °C and 1.72 °C, respectively, were recorded outside the BTES at 6 m depth (Fig.2).

The results of the sensitivity analysis and the averaged COP for the worst/best-case scenarios are shown in Table 2. The most influential parameters inducing a relative COP gain/loss > 1 % in the 30% scenarios are parameters 1, 2, 5, 9, 10, 16 and 17 (Tab.2). The least influential parameters inducing a relative COP gain/loss < 0.1 % in the 30% scenarios are parameters 7, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 (Tab.2). The worst-case scenario averaged a COP of 2.74 while the best-case scenario averaged a COP of 3.05.

Figure 2. Base case scenario's simulated temperature and COP.

Table 2. Sensitivity of input parameters on averaged COP.

Base case scenario		2.92			
Worst case scenario		2.74			
Best case scenario		3.05			
Category	Parameter	COP difference from initial scenario (%)			
		-30% scenario	-10% scenario	+10% scenario	+30% scenario
(A)	(1)	-0.68	-0.64	-1.45	-1.88
	(2)	-1.05	-0.84	-0.66	-0.53
	(3)	-1.06	-0.87	-0.81	-0.78
	(4)	+0.28	+0.06	-0.03	-0.06
	(5)	-	-	-2.27	-4.87
(B)	(6)	+0.48	+0.16	-0.15	-0.46
	(7)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	(8)	+0.27	+0.06	-0.03	-0.06
	(9)	+2.80	+0.78	-0.66	-1.72
	(10)	-1.42	-0.37	+0.30	+0.74
(C)	(11)	+0.05	+0.01	-0.02	-0.05
	(12)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	(13)	-0.05	-0.02	+0.02	+0.05
(D)	(14)	+0.05	+0.02	-0.01	-0.05
	(15)	+0.06	+0.02	-0.01	-0.03
(E)	(16)	+4.67	+1.51	-1.57	-4.46
	(17)	-4.64	-1.55	+1.56	+4.68

4. Discussion

Simulated temperature and calculated COP (Fig.2) show that there is no cumulative thermal energy gain or loss within 6 years. The simulated temperature of the heat carrier fluid and the COP reached an equilibrium suggesting that the BTES internal temperature is affected by seasonal surface temperature fluctuations due to the low depth of the BTES (12 m). However, the BTES cannot only rely on the seasonal temperature recharge during summer since the heat pump inlet fluid reaches a minimum temperature of -6.3 °C which is too close to the heat pump lower operating temperature threshold of -6.7 °C (Fig.2). The sensitivity analysis shows that the BTES performance can be significantly improved or decreased according to uncertainties of the input parameters. For example, the best-case scenario, which averaged a COP of 3.05 (Tab.2), can provide 265 GJ in

energy savings with respect to the no-BTES case over 4 years of production, compared to 252 GJ for the worst-case scenario (COP of 2.74) and 245 GJ for the no-heat injection scenario (COP of 2.65; Fig.2). This difference, mainly due to various BTES configurations and geological properties (Tab.2), is expected to rise with increasing BTES volume.

Due to the short BHE length, the internal temperature of the BTES is affected by surface temperature variations and could potentially decrease if there is no snow cover insulating during the winter. Therefore, BHE layout is an important consideration to ensure the performance of this small-scale BTES. Specific storage does not have any influence on the results due to the assumption of a fully confined aquifer in order to simplify the numerical model. This assumption seems reasonable since porosity is a low and the granitic aquifer under study has a low capacity to store water. In addition, thermal conductivity of the heat carrier fluid does not affect the BTES because its effects are included into the borehole thermal resistance calculation in FEFLOW to simplify the analysis. Simulated scenarios did not include parameter interdependency and may sometimes be unrepresentative. Parameters interdependency should be considered in a BTES design when materials and configurations are chosen based on thermal and hydrogeological in situ conditions of the studied site. For example, a permeable aquifer with significant hydraulic conductivity can have a greater effect on the BTES's performance assessment. Indeed, the base case scenario with a greater hydraulic conductivity value would increase COP variations for the sensitivity analysis. Technical details of the ecoGEO 1-9 kW heat pump did not consider a propylene glycol-water mixture to calculate the COP. In fact, this mixture would induce a lower heat pump's COP. However, current results provide an initial assessment of the parameters influencing the BTES' performance with respect to the specific small-scale BTES studied in Whapmagoostui-Kuujjuarapik.

5. Conclusions

This study presented a sensitivity analysis of the main parameters affecting the operation of a BTES for a small residential building in Whapmagoostui-Kuujjuarapik, northern Quebec. BTES configuration, subsurface thermal properties and heat injection/extraction rate are the most influential parameters to consider for BTES design. The sensitivity analysis provided a better understanding of the parameters involved in the design of a BTES operated in a subarctic climate in order to help the implementation of sustainable green energies in this northern community. Future activities will simulate

technical details of a heat pump considering a propylene glycol-water mixture to calculate the COP, an artificial insulation at the top of the BTES to analyze heat transfer effects and an in-depth analysis of the energy yearly profil. Methods and tools developed in the present study will also be useful to anticipate BTES efficiency and optimize the design at any latitude worldwide.

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GEOTHERMAL EXPLORATION AT MOUNT MEAGER, SOUTHWESTERN BC: A RESISTIVITY MODEL FROM 3-D INVERSION OF MAGNETOTELLURIC DATA

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Abstract

The Garibaldi volcanic belt in British Columbia is part of the ring of fire, a belt of volcanic activity that surrounds the Pacific Ocean. Many countries in this region produce electricity from hot water extracted from geothermal reservoirs found beneath these volcanoes, and Canada could do the same. The most recent volcanic activity in the Garibaldi belt occurred 2340 ± 50 years ago at Mount Meager. Steam vents on this volcano have become emergent in recent years due to glacial recession and major landslides have occurred, including an event in 2010 that remains Canada's largest recorded landslide.

Geothermal research has taken place at Mount Meager since the 1970s. To reduce the economic risks of development, additional information about the geothermal reservoir and natural hazards is needed. Geophysical studies of the subsurface are part of the required data collection.

In 2019 and 2020, magnetotelluric data were collected in the region around Mount Meager. They were used to generate a 3-D model of electrical resistivity, a property that is sensitive to the presence of fluids. This model gives valuable information about the size of the geothermal reservoir and location of the magma body beneath this active volcano.

1. Introduction

The study area is situated toward the northern end of a chain of volcanoes that extends along much of western North America. Offshore southwestern British Columbia (BC), Canada and northwestern Washington, U.S.A., the Juan de Fuca plate subducts beneath the North American plate at the Cascadia subduction zone (Fig. 1). The tectonic convergence rate between these two plates is ~ 4 cm/year (Kreemer et al., 2014). Dehydration reactions in the subducting slab release volatiles into the overlying mantle of the North American plate, lowering its melting point and creating a region of partial melt, which leads to volcanism at the surface above (Stern, 2002).

The chain of volcanoes resulting from this subduction is called the Cascade volcanic arc. The northernmost segment (shown in Fig. 1) trends roughly NW-SE, whereas the rest of the arc (not shown) generally trends N-S. The northern segment is 300-400 km inboard of the trench, while the southern segments are 250-300 km inboard (Hickson, 1994). Mount Baker is the most voluminous volcanic complex in Fig. 1, Glacier Peak is the most-recently active with an eruption in the mid-1700s, and Mount Meager is the most-recently active in Canada with a major eruption ~ 2400 years ago (Hickson, 1994). The most recent volcanism in the northern arc has been rhyolitic-to-dacitic at Mount Meager, dacitic at Mount Cayley and Mount Garibaldi, and andesitic at Mount Baker and Glacier Peak (Hickson, 1994). This illustrates a change from felsic composition in the north to intermediate silica content in the south.

The northern segment of the volcanic arc, extending from Glacier Peak to Silverthorne, is called the Garibaldi volcanic belt; and the southern segment, from Mount Rainier in central Washington to Mount Lassen in northern California, is called the High Cascades (Mullen et al., 2017).

Fig. 1. Map of southwestern BC and northwestern Washington. Major volcanic centers of the Garibaldi Volcanic Belt are shown as triangles. Cities and towns are shown as squares.

The Mount Meager area drew attention in the 1970s as a geothermal target because of two thermal spring systems, Meager Creek springs and Pebble Creek spring (Souther, 1981). Early work included geothermometry, DC resistivity, and diamond drilling (Fairbank et al., 1981). Lewis and Jessop (1981) measured heat flow of 132 mW/m² in a drill hole near Mount Meager, compared with a mean of 79 mW/m² in three drill holes each more than 10 km from Mount Meager. Based on these studies, this volcano is one of the most promising geothermal targets near to infrastructure in Canada and has been the subject of research since the 1970s (Jessop, 1998). However, a number of barriers to development have been identified and need to be addressed.

One challenge at Mount Meager has been the distance to the power grid. This has improved in recent years since Innergex Renewable Energy Inc. has been operating two run-of-river hydroelectric plants near Mount Meager since 2017, as part of their Upper Lillooet River Hydro Project. The larger of the two (81.4 MW), the Upper Lillooet River facility, is 5 km northeast of Mount Meager and the Boulder Creek facility (25.3 MW) is located 7 km east of Mount Meager. Electricity generated at these two facilities is transmitted to the BC Hydro transmission system by a 230 kV transmission line (www.innergex.com/sites/boulder-creek). The proximity of this high-voltage line to Meager Creek has increased the economic feasibility of a potential geothermal power plant in the area, however, it is up to Innergex whether they wish to enter into a corporate relationship with any geothermal developers.

Another challenge comes from landslide hazards. A large rockslide and debris flow at Mount Meager on August 6, 2010 displaced 48.5 million cubic metres of material (Allstadt, 2013; Guthrie et al., 2012). Meager Creek was temporarily dammed, and the flood risk led to the evacuation of 1500 Pemberton residents (Guthrie et al., 2012). Therefore, landslide hazard assessment is an important consideration for ongoing geothermal development at Mount Meager.

A remaining challenge comes from uncertainties in the permeability and porosity of the rocks in the reservoir. This question can be addressed with geophysical studies that image the subsurface structure, as described in this paper. The central part of the paper is a 3-D resistivity model derived from inversion of magnetotelluric data. It is part of a multidisciplinary research program that includes magnetotellurics, passive seismic, gravity, bedrock mapping, fracture analysis, and thermal-spring geochemistry (Grasby et al., 2020).

2. Methods

The magnetotelluric (MT) method uses natural electromagnetic (EM) signals to image the electrical resistivity of the subsurface and is widely used in geothermal exploration (Muñoz, 2014). The low-frequency radio wave sources are generated by global lightning activity and interactions between the solar wind and the Earth's ionosphere. This EM method measures time series of electric and magnetic fields at the surface of the Earth, then converts them into frequency-domain transfer functions (TFs) that describe the impedance of the Earth. These TFs are used to calculate the electrical resistivity at depth. The theoretical foundations of the MT method were developed by Cagniard (1953) and a detailed description is given by Chave & Jones (2012).

The MT method has two main advantages that make it suitable for geothermal exploration:

- 1) It can effectively image aqueous and magmatic fluids, both of which are relevant to geothermal exploration. The electrical resistivity of the crust varies over several orders of magnitude: dry crystalline rock has a resistivity in excess of 1000 Ωm, whereas the presence of aqueous fluids or partial melt can lower this to values in the range 1-10 Ωm. Thus, MT data can help distinguish fluid-rich zones.
- 2) It can resolve crustal features over a broad range of depths allowing for investigation of both fine-scale crustal structure and deeper resistivity anomalies. The frequency of the passive radio wave source controls the depth of exploration according to the skin depth (δ) which is defined in metres as: $\delta \cong 500\sqrt{\rho T}$, where ρ is the bulk resistivity and T is the period of the signal. Therefore, longer periods give information about deeper structures and signals are more attenuated in lower resistivity materials. This broad depth range is a distinct advantage over other EM methods that are more limited in scale.

Resistivity models derived from MT data are an excellent way to detect fluids, although other causes of low resistivity such as hydrothermal alteration minerals (Hersir et al., 2015; Ussher et al., 2000), graphite films (Frost et al., 1989) and sulphide minerals (Varentsov et al., 2013) must also be considered. Additional geophysical and geological data are helpful in distinguishing between different low-resistivity materials.

The techniques available for the analysis of MT data have drastically improved over the past decade due to increased computing power. In the past, 1-D and 2-D inversions were used to derive models of sub-surface

resistivity from MT data, but this greatly limited the application of the method in complex geological environments. MT data can now be inverted to produce 3-D resistivity models with new inversion codes that are run on multi-processor clusters (Kelbert et al., 2014; Lindsey & Newman, 2015).

The available broadband MT data were recorded at 73 MT stations in the region 50.48 to 50.74°N and 123.29 to 123.71°W, as shown in Fig. 2. These data included seven soundings collected in 1982 by the Pacific Geoscience Centre (Flores-Luna, 1986), 31 soundings collected in 2000 by Frontier Geosciences Inc. (Candy, 2001), and 35 soundings collected by the University of Alberta for this study.

The University of Alberta took MT measurements at 23 sites in 2019 (Unsworth et al., 2020) and 12 sites in 2020. These time series were processed using robust algorithms (Egbert & Eisler, 1998) based on the theory of Egbert and Booker (1986). These frequency-domain data were edited manually to remove outliers.

The preliminary model presented in Section 3 was obtained from joint inversion of impedance and tipper data using 29 periods (0.0025-1000 s) and 66 locations (Fig. 3). The locations consist of two from 1982, 30 from 2000, 22 from 2019, and 12 from 2020. An inversion with 64 locations (2000-2020 data) and another with 34 locations (2019-2020 data) will be performed to test the robustness of the model and possible influence of time variations. However, 20-40 years is a relatively small amount of time when considering the evolution of a magma body and its associated hydrothermal systems.

A 5% relative error floor was applied to the impedance data and a 0.03 absolute error floor was applied to the tipper data. A 3-D inversion algorithm called ModEM (Kelbert et al., 2014) is freely available for academic use and was used here. The inversion started from a 100 Ωm half-space with an r.m.s. misfit of 11.7 and converged to a resistivity model with a misfit of 2.0 after 670 iterations.

The rectangular model mesh used in this study had 2.1 million cells: 148 in the north-south direction, 136 in the east-west direction, and 105 in the vertical direction. The cells were 250 x 250 m in the horizontal plane, with 15 padding cells increasing geometrically by a factor of 1.35 away from the central grid (Fig. 3). The upper layers were 50 m thick, then layer thickness increased geometrically by a factor of 1.1 below topography. The top 12 layers, higher than all the MT sites, were removed to decrease the total model size and the computing resources needed.

Fig. 2. Map of the study area with all available MT data locations.

Fig. 3. Map of the study area with MT data locations included in the preliminary inversion.

3. Results and Discussion

This model is preliminary, as discussed in Section 4. The uppermost kilometre of the Mount Meager massif is characterized by low resistivity (Fig. 4a), likely caused by saline aqueous fluids (brines) and hydrothermally altered rocks.

There is a large conductor at 5-8 km below sea level, between Mount Meager and Meager Creek (Fig. 4b). It is > 7 km wide (Fig. 5a), > 10 km long (Fig. 5b), and > 3 km thick. This anomaly is likely caused by brines and partially melted rocks, and it occurs beneath the areas investigated in 1982 and 2000 (Fig. 2). The finer details of the model may change as the model is refined, but this large feature is certainly robust.

Fig. 4. Horizontal layers of the 3-D resistivity model at (a) 1.7 km above sea level and (b) 6.7 km below sea level. Cross-sections indicated by lines A-A' and B-B' are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Vertical slices of the 3-D resistivity model from south to north (A-A') and west to east (B-B').

4. Future Work and Conclusions

The resistivity model presented in the previous section is preliminary and the following steps are currently underway or in planning: (1) variation of smoothing parameters, e.g., regularization parameter (λ) and covariance; (2) testing of different data subsets; and (3) testing of data sensitivity and model resolution, e.g., forward modelling and synthetic inversions.

After the resistivity model has been finalized, more detailed interpretations will be made and will include: (1) estimation of fluid content and relevant parameters using constraints from geophysical and chemical experiments, (2) estimation of melt fraction using constraints from petrological experiments, and (3) joint interpretations using results from the gravity and seismic investigations.

Two general conclusions are very likely at this early stage: (1) there are near-surface brines and hydrothermally altered rocks beneath the Mount Meager massif, and (2) there is a magma body beneath the Mount Meager massif in the depth range 7-10 km. Detailed descriptions of these features will require further analysis, but this result is not

inconsistent with the youthfulness of the last volcanic episode, the degree of hydrothermal alteration seen in the near surface as a result of the landslide failures, and the long lived fumaroles (Hickson, 2017; Hickson et al., 1999; Stewart et al., 2003). Implications for geothermal development are also being developed.

Audio-magnetotelluric (AMT) data were also collected in 2019 (Craven et al., 2020) and this regional model will assist the AMT interpretations.

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STRUCTURAL GEOLOGY CONSTRAINTS AND ITS INFLUENCE ON GEOTHERMAL SYSTEMS AT MT. MEAGER, BRITISH COLUMBIA

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Abstract

The Garibaldi Volcanic Belt (GVB), and particularly the Mount Meager Volcanic Complex (MMVC), has been identified as a region with significant geothermal potential (e.g., Ghomshei et al., 2004, 2005; Arianpoo, 2009). Although geothermal exploration at Mount Meager was carried out intermittently from the early 1970s through to 2009, the previous studies did not constrain the influence of major structural and tectonic features on the geothermal fluid pathways. In this study, we used classic structural field geology mapping of structures such as faults, folds, and other fractures along with paleomagnetic inclination of young volcanic units to constrain the neotectonic activity of structures at Mount Meager; the goal was to help define the current structural geology elements controlling geothermal pathways in the region. Our preliminary study indicates significant tilting and minor rotation of both older basement rocks and younger volcanic rocks as young as 300-700 ka or between 2-1.2 Ma. The tilting and rotation of basement and young volcanic rocks was most likely controlled by a newer fault strand of the Owl Creek fault and movement on the left-lateral strike slip fault between the east and west ridges of North Lillooet Ridge. Hence, potential geothermal fluid pathways, at least north of the Mount Meager complex, are controlled largely by kinematics of the Owl Creek fault and the mapped left-lateral strike slip fault between the east and west ridges of North Lillooet Ridge, north of the Mount Meager massif. The current findings will significantly enhance our understanding of the geothermal reservoir at MMVC and can be used as essential input data for 3D reservoir modelling.

1. Introduction

Geothermal energy with its limited environmental impact is considered as a particularly appealing energy source. However, development costs and large uncertainties regarding the presence of a good quality subsurface reservoir (e.g., sufficient geothermal heat storage and geothermal fluid pathways), can bring substantial economic risk. For instance, unproductive or failed boreholes can in fact negatively sway the economic plan. The usual mitigation steps for such uncertainties include

Figure 1. A) Geology of the southern Coast Mountains and surrounding areas (after Bustin et al., 2013). B) Subset showing Mount Meager geology and Owl Creek Fault. EKvs: Lower Cretaceous Gambier group; CD: Cadwallader Group; Czg: Plutonic rocks (37 to 8 Ma); m: Protolith unknown (metamorphic rock); Eg: Plutonic rock (55 to 45 Ma); IKg: plutonic rocks (85 to 65 Ma). Note: juxtaposition of CD to EKvs indicate that OCF must be active prior to or coeval with the Miocene intrusions. C) Bouguer gravity modelling along line D-D' (from Bustin et al., 2013). The yellow star represents approximate location of North Lillooet ridge.

evaluating reservoir capacity, zones of permeability, fracture, or fault patterns, which ultimately can reduce the exploration risk.

Various authors studied the role of structural geology in geothermal exploration (Philipp et al., 2007; Moeck, 2014; Filipovich et al., 2020; Liotta et al., 2021). The aforementioned studies all agree regarding the essential role of structural geology in maximizing the likelihood of a successful geothermal project; specifically in reservoirs that require permeability enhancement (i.e., Enhanced Geothermal Reservoir Projects).

Philipp et al. (2007) studied the influence of structural geology and particularly the role of constraining the stress field to simulate an enhanced geothermal system in Buntsandstein, northern Germany. They found that the stress field controls the fault slip and fluid transport. Hence, the stress field can determine if and how fractures propagate or if fractures opened up rather than closed. For instance, if the maximum horizontal compressive stress becomes parallel to the strike of the fractures; fractures tend to open and thus fluid transport is enhanced. Alternatively, if the maximum horizontal compressive stress is perpendicular to strike of the fractures, various fractures may close reducing fluid transport. Therefore, it is important to understand the major geologic structures and timing of the latest tectonic activity that shaped the subsurface geothermal reservoir. This will help to assess not only the reservoir quality but also define the geothermal fluid pathways.

The Mount Meager Volcanic Complex (MMVC), comprises the northern most volcanic centre of the Garibaldi Volcanic Belt (GVB). MMVC contains basement complex and young volcanic rocks. The basement complex includes older unknown age high-grade metamorphic rocks, late Triassic Cadwallader group, late Jurassic to late Cretaceous intrusive rocks, late Cretaceous sedimentary rocks of the Gambier group and Paleogene to Miocene intrusive rocks.

The young volcanic rocks were emplaced during three different stages (Read, 1990): 1) Pliocene to Pleistocene rhyodacite (2-1 Ma); 2) early Pleistocene to late Pleistocene dacite to andesite-basalt (1-0.3 Ma); and 3) Late Pleistocene to Holocene and recent rhyodacite to dacite composition (0.3-0 Ma).

During the last ~1.9 Ma, volcanic eruptions at Mount Meager become younger from south to north, and a relatively young east-west striking extensional fault has been mapped along Meager Creek (Appendix 2). The existence of this fault is well-documented through bedrock exposure mapping, fracture data, drilled core and refraction seismic data (Fairbank et al., 1980, 1981). Although the Meager Creek fault zone is mapped as an

extensional fault, the presence of mylonite found in drill holes suggests a compressional component (Fairbank et al., 1980, 1981). This may indicate the Meager Creek fault zone experienced multiple episodes of deformation.

In general, three types of faulting identified at Mount Meager include those related to tectonic stress such as Owl Creek fault (Fig. 1), faults related to volcanism and faults related to mass creep and gravitational failure (Fairbank et al., 1980, 1981). For geothermal exploration, the most important structures are those controlled by regional tectonics followed by fault structures related to volcanism and they can play a major role in facilitating pathways for geothermal fluids.

Geologic mapping, seismic section profiles and Bouguer gravity modelling (Bustin et al., 2013) (Fig. 1) approximately 15 km south-southeast of Mount Meager suggest that the Owl Creek fault may have been active during the emplacement of at least the Miocene granitic intrusions (Fig. 1). We therefore need to understand the kinematic history (whether magmatism was emplaced syn or post tectonic deformation) and the kinematic compatibility (whether the current deformation or faulting is geometrically compatible) with the different periods of magmatic emplacement.

Paleomagnetic directional data can be used to determine displacement, rotation and/or tilting of fault blocks. This technique is more convenient and accurate where structural data can be measured such as in sedimentary rocks. However, its application becomes more difficult in basement rocks where accurate bedding measurements are not feasible. A more detailed explanation of paleomagnetism techniques as it applies to structural geology and petrophysics can be found in the literature (Beck et al., 1986; Enkin, 2003; Butler, 2004; Richards et al., 2004a, 2004b). Here we carry out a pilot paleomagnetic study of the structural units of importance in the Mount Meager geothermal study.

The work in the MMVC involved 1) obtaining post-deformational paleomagnetic directions and comparing these with the expected Geocentric Axial Dipole (GAD) field direction for the sampling latitude, and 2) establishing the age of measured geomagnetic polarities. Furthermore, radiometric dating of young volcanic rocks will assist in identifying displaced fault blocks and making assumptions about their reconstruction to a pre-deformation stage.

We aim to document the major structural geology features controlling the geothermal fluid pathway through 1) classic structural field geology mapping of faults, folds, and fractures of basement and young volcanic units (summer 2019 field work) (Fig. 2); 2)

Paleomagnetic directions of basement and young volcanic units (summer 2020 field work) (Figs. 3, 4; Table 1); and 3) Geochronological dating for the drilled paleomagnetism samples to reconstruct the displaced structural geology features and define the sequence of events (in progress); at this stage we use published geochronology age dates from Woodsworth (1977) and Read (1990) as well as, ages of paleomagnetic polarity (Fig. 3; Table 1).

2. Methods

During the summer of 2019, further exploration of Mount Meager's geothermal potential was initiated with two weeks of geology field mapping, north of Mount Meager, on the northern Lillooet ridge. We mapped both young volcanic rocks and basement rocks and collected structural data such as faults, folds, fractures, and attitude of bedding and planar features (Figs. 2, 4). A detailed structural geology analysis is published in chapter two of Geoscience BC 2020 technical report (Harris et al., 2020).

During the Summer 2020, we conducted additional field campaigns which included a paleomagnetic study of young volcanic rocks; the goal was to constrain and verify whether tilting and/or rotation within basement rocks predates or postdates the youngest Quaternary volcanism within MMVC. Additionally, four rock samples were sent to the Geochronology lab at Oregon State University (USA) in order to enable a better differentiation between fractures and faults related to volcanism, and faults controlled by regional tectonics.

Samples for paleomagnetic analysis were collected from both basement and younger volcanic rocks at two ridges, the east Lillooet ridge and west Lillooet ridge north of the Mount Meager massif. A portable gasoline-powered rock drill with water swivel attachment was used to drill 2.5 cm diameter cylindrical cores. Due to time and budget limitations, five sites were initially chosen for this pilot study. Eight cores were collected at each site over an area of 5-10 m to reduce the potential errors from lightening or minor local movements along joints, etc. Additionally, all samples were oriented using both a solar and magnetic compass to preclude orientation error due to compass deflection by strongly magnetized rocks at the outcrop. The samples were analyzed at the paleomagnetic laboratory of the University of Lethbridge, Alberta. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Sapphire Instruments (SI-2B) susceptibility meter. The magnetization of each sample was measured with an AGICO JR-6A spinner magnetometer prior to demagnetization and again after each level of stepwise demagnetization. Samples were kept in magnetic shields

following field collection and between laboratory measurements. Most samples were subjected to alternating field demagnetization with one-third of the collection subjected to thermal demagnetization. Alternating field demagnetization was performed using an ASC Scientific D-2000 demagnetizer with a three-axis manual tumbler and carried out at 10 milli-tesla (mT) steps (up to 100 mT).

Thermal demagnetization was carried out at 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, and 550 °C, using an ASC Model TD48 dual-chamber thermal demagnetizer to determine whether or not alternating field demagnetization was sufficient to resolve the primary remanence. AF Demagnetization was sufficient to resolve the primary remanence for most samples but for basement rocks (granite-diorites) thermal demagnetization was required. Directions of characteristic remanent magnetization were determined for each sample by principal component analysis (Kirschvink, 1980) using Remasoft version 3.0 (Chadima and Hrouda, 2006). Mean characteristic remanent magnetization directions were calculated for each site and an overall mean was also calculated.

3. Results

Paleomagnetic samples were drilled at the following five sites (Fig. 4): On the eastern ridge, site 1 and site 2 were drilled on the undated andesitic lava, with site 1 stratigraphically located above site 2; site 3 was drilled on pink granite basement rock which was in sharp contact with the andesitic lava (Fig. 4). On the western ridge, site 4 was drilled on the large vertically jointed dacite lava flow; site 5 was drilled on older basement granodiorite rocks. Below is a summary of the results:

- 1) Field geology data including outcrop scale, structural geology (faults, folds, joints and attitude of basement units) mapped on the north Lillooet Ridge, north of the Mount Meager massif indicate the presence of an E-W striking left-lateral strike-slip fault between east and west ridges at North Lillooet Ridges (detailed structural geology published in Harris et al., 2020).
- 2) Preliminary paleomagnetic directional study for the young volcanic rocks (between 2 Ma to 0 Ma) is in agreement with the presence of a left-lateral strike slip fault and suggests an anticlockwise rotation of approximately 10 to 20 degrees.
- 3) The current paleomagnetic data, along with the structural geologic fieldwork including cross-cutting relationships of faults within the basement and younger lavas, indicates that both dacitic and andesitic lava flows on the North

Lillooet ridge either predate faulting or were emplaced during faulting.

- 4) If our preliminary pilot paleomagnetic results are accurate, Mount Meager and more specifically,

North Lillooet ridge, was tectonically active at least between 300-700 ka or between 2-1.2 Ma

4. Discussion

The North Lillooet ridge includes basement rocks such as granodiorite as old as 47 to 55 Ma, mostly outcropping on the western ridge (Fig. 1) and pink granitic rocks as old as 8 Ma (possibly Salal pluton), outcropping on the eastern ridge (Woodsworth, 1977). Additionally, younger undated basaltic and andesitic lava occur on the eastern ridge and dacite, rhyodacite and andesite lavas are located on western ridge. Although the younger lava on the North Lillooet ridge is not yet dated, the ages indicated on the regional geology map for the young volcanic lava (Woodsworth, 1977; Read, 1990) on Mount Meager suggest ages of < 2 Ma as follow: 1) Pliocene to Pleistocene rhyodacite (2-1) Ma; 2) early Pleistocene to late Pleistocene dacite to andesitic-basalt (1-0.3) Ma; and 3) Late Pleistocene to Holocene and recent rhyodacite to dacite composition (0.3-0) Ma. Hence, the expected age range for the young lava at North Lillooet ridge should lie between 2 Ma to 0 Ma.

Sites 1, 2, 3 and 4 are stably magnetized (Fig. 5). Sites 1-3 are reversely magnetized and given the suggested ages, would fall within the Matuyama Reversed Chron. Site 4 is normally magnetized, and given its suggested age, falls within the Brunhes Normal Chron.

Site 5 does not provide a reliable directional mean following AF demagnetization. It is weakly magnetized, and exhibits a soft, multi-domain remanence upon AF demagnetization. Two samples were thermally demagnetized and show a stable component between 400-550 °C (See Appendix). More samples will need to be collected for thermal demagnetization. Hence, site 5 is excluded, pending further sampling.

While absolute ages are not yet available for these paleomagnetic sites, approximate ages for the samples based on the dated rocks nearby (Woodsworth, 1977; Read, 1979, 1990), as well as outcrop field relationships and polarity data allow for some preliminary estimates. Sites 1 and 2 collected on the eastern ridge in the andesitic lava are reversely magnetized; they are thought to be associated with the nearby andesitic lavas of similar chemistry which have an age range of 0.78-0.9 Ma or 1.06-1.78 Ma and therefore sites 1 and 2 fall within the Late Matuyama reversed Chron (1.78-0.78 Ma). These two sites may show a slight rotation of approximately 10 to 20 degrees anticlockwise, although it is not impossible that secular variation may account for this southeasterly declination (Fig.5; Table 1). Site 3 samples are from the pink granite basement rocks on the eastern ridge and are

Figure 2. A) 3 m resolution PlanetScope satellite image draped over 1.5 m Digital Elevation Model (from historical aerial photos) with mapped outcrops and structures. B) Rose diagram for strike and trend of measured structural data; green, shows strike orientation of faults; blue, strike orientation of basement units; black strike orientation of joint, fractures and veins; red trend of minor folds. Stereographic contours show the density of the data per cluster for poles of strike of structural features such as fault, joints/fractures, and beddings. Note: The differences in trends of faults, folds, and joints on both east and west ridges; this might indicate tilting and/or rotation of rocks.

reversely magnetized. Based on field observations, this site is tentatively correlated to the Salal pluton (8 Ma). Similar to sites 1 and 2, site 3 shows a possible anticlockwise rotation of 10-20 degrees (Fig. 5; Table 1). However, given the nearly identical directions of Sites 1 to 3 and the proximity of site 3 (basement rock) to sites 1

the fault; and the eastern ridge which may show approximately 10-20-degree anticlockwise rotation to the east, resembles the hanging wall of the fault.

The current paleomagnetic data, along with the structural geologic fieldwork including cross-cutting relationship of faults with the basement and younger lava flows, indicates that both dacitic and andesitic lava flows on the North Lillooet ridge either predate faulting or were emplaced during faulting. Therefore, Mount Meager, more specifically, North Lillooet ridge was tectonically active at least between 300-700 ka or between 2-1.2 Ma. These dates will be refined with the addition of the geochronology analyses. Our data compares favorably with the regional geology map (Bustin et al., 2013; Fig. 1) which suggests that young volcanic rocks become younger from south to north on Mount Meager. The most distinctive regional tectonic fault is the Owl Creek fault. The mapped cross cutting relationships and position of metamorphic rocks (unknown age, unit m on Fig. 2) are of various ages, i.e., units Eg (55 to 45 Ma) and unit Czg (37 to 8 Ma) and this likely suggests that the Owl Creek fault was active on several occasions between 55 Ma to 8 Ma. Additionally, the tilting and rotation of basement and young volcanic rocks was most likely controlled by a newer fault strand of the Owl Creek fault and movement on the left-lateral strike slip fault between the east and west ridges of North Lillooet Ridge. In conclusion, potential geothermal fluid pathways, at least north of the Mount Meager complex, are likely to be controlled by the kinematics of the Owl Creek fault and the mapped left-lateral strike slip fault between the east and west ridges of North Lillooet ridge, north of the Mount Meager massif (Figs. 2, 4).

Table 1. Principle Component Analysis (PCA) for the selected paleomagnetism sites and interpretation of paleomagnetic direction of samples at each site. Notes: NC=number of samples collected; NU=number of samples used in calculation; D=declination; I=inclination; α_{95} = radius of 95% circle of confidence; k=precision parameter; P=geomagnetic polarity (N is Normal and R is Reverse) directions.

Site	NC	NU	D (°)	I (°)	α_{95} (°)	k	P	Possible Tilting	Possible Rotation	Rock Type	Approx. Age
1	8	8	134.9	-66.5	4.3	164.7	R	NA	10-20°	Andesitic Lava	0.78-0.9 Ma or 1.06-1.78 Ma
2	8	6	134.9	-68.3	2.7	610.1	R	NA	10-20°	Andesitic Lava	0.78-0.9 Ma or 1.06-1.78 Ma
3	8	8	136.7	-65.6	3.9	179.3	R	NA	10-20°	Salal Pluton?	~8 Ma
4	8	6	352.5	29.8	4	274.6	N	>25°	NA	Dacitic Lava	0.3-0 Ma or 2-1.2 Ma
5	8	5	134	19	14	30.5	N	>40°	10-20°	Granodiorite	55-47 Ma

Figure 3. Reversals of Earth's magnetic field for the last 11 Ma (Pliocene-Pleistocene and late Miocene). Dark bands indicate times when the Earth's magnetic field matches that of today, i.e., a normal magnetic field. White bands signify times when the Earth's magnetic field was reversed - reversed polarity. Paleomagnetic ages assigned to samples collected at sites 1 to 4 based on Read (1990) and Woodsworth (1977) age classification of young volcanic rocks on the Mount Meager massif.

and 2 (andesitic lava), it is possible that the basement rocks were thermally remagnetized (reset) by the eruption of the andesitic lava.

Site 4 samples collected on the western ridge in the dacitic lava reveal normal geomagnetic polarity. The nearby dacitic lavas have age ranges of 2-1.78 Ma or 0.3-0 Ma. Unlike other sites, this site does not show any rotation but does show significant tilting (shallowing of the paleomagnetic inclination by approximately 30 degrees northward) (Fig. 5; Table 1).

The preliminary paleomagnetic data (including possible rotation and significant tilting) is compatible with the presence of a suggested left-lateral strike slip fault between the west and east ridges at the North Lillooet ridge, north of the Mount Meager massif (Fig. 2). The western ridge which shows no rotation, but significant tilting (~30 degrees northward), resembles the footwall of

Figure 4. Bedrock geology map for the North Lillooet ridge, north of the Mount Meager; green dots show sites of paleomagnetism samples. At each site, a minimum of 8 samples were collected. Modified from Harris et al. (2020).

Figure 5. Stereographic projections of data points (black) and mean, including error circle (in red).

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Appendix One

Examples of some demagnetization data obtained from more than 38 samples of sites 1 to 5 at North Lillooet ridge (Note: Even though, Site 5 was excluded from our data interpretation but below for further clarity; we presented AF and Thermal Demagnetization for Site 5 as well). For each sample, the stereographic plots (left figures) show magnetization directions after stepwise demagnetization, where the filled circles lie on the lower hemisphere. The orthogonal plots (right figures) show horizontal projections as filled circles and vertical projections as open circles. Both alternating field and thermal demagnetization plots are given. Units are in amperes per metre.

Site 2

SFU009A
N/A

SFU009B
Thermal demag

Site 3

SFU024A
N/A

SFU024B
Thermal demag

Site 4

SFU031A
N/A

SFU031B
Thermal demag

Site 5

SFU035A
N/A

SFU035B
Thermal demag

Appendix Two: Shows pattern of faults within and around Mount Meager. Areas indicated with red box mapped during summers 2019 and 2020.

Appendix Two Remarks:

The above map show distributions and patterns of regional faults within mount Meager Volcanic Complex (MMVC). Two potential geothermal reservoirs identified within MMVC. The northern Reservoir located at the footwalls of Owl Creek fault system and the southern reservoir located at the vicinity of a fault system within and nearby Meager Creek area.

In this study, we documented major structural geology structures (Near the Northern Reservoir) in terms of the timing (kinematic history) and geometry of the structural geology features (Kinematic compatibility). We used both outcrop mapping of geologic structures and paleomagnetic study of structures of interest to define timing of latest tectonic activity that formed the fault system.

This knowledge can be used to perform proper steps to increase the permeability of the basement rocks through a process called induced fracture method. In order to successfully generate useful fracture system that increase fluid circulation within the reservoir; its essential to have accurate understanding of the fault system in the region. This study is meant to serve as foundation to understand the patterns of faults and fault system distribution in MMVC.

Although, in this study we partially mapped faults within the southern reservoir, but the mapped area is complemented by the previous works in the region. At this stage, we were unable to perform detail analysis for faults within the southern reservoir because we need to have reasonable age constraints of structures. The age constraints of the structures can be performed through paleomagnetic sampling and radiometric dating for structures of interest.

Combining Magnetotelluric and Well-log Data to Improve Resistivity Models: Implications for Geothermal Exploration in the Western Canadian Sedimentary Basin

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Keywords: geophysics, electromagnetics, magnetotellurics, well-logs, inversion, geothermal, sedimentary basin

Abstract

Sedimentary basins host significant geothermal resources with temperatures that can be high enough for both direct use and power generation. Several power plants are under development in the Western Canadian Sedimentary Basin (WCSB). Ongoing development of this type of geothermal resource will benefit from more reliable information about subsurface properties. This includes information about structure within the basin and about aquifers that host the geothermal reservoir and underlying structures in the crystalline basement rocks.

Resistivity is a useful property to measure in geothermal exploration because of its sensitivity to the presence of fluids. It can be measured with electromagnetic methods on a range of spatial scales. Regional scale structures have been determined using magnetotellurics (MT), but the models generated can suffer from non-uniqueness. A significant amount of well-log data has been collected during extensive oil-and-gas exploration in the WCSB. By combining surface electromagnetic measurements with well-log data, an enhanced resistivity model can be found.

In the Peace River area, in Northwest Alberta, there is demand for the direct use of geothermal heat in both district heating and industrial processing. This motivated the University of Alberta to collect tw

o profiles of MT data to investigate the structure of the sedimentary basin and crystalline basement. The MT data were inverted using a 2-D approach. A second resistivity model was created by smoothing and interpolating resistivity well-logs. The two data sets were then used in a set of joint inversions to improve resolution of structures within the sedimentary basin and underlying crystalline basement. We will show that this process allows resistivity structures in the sedimentary basin to be more reliably imaged.

1. Introduction

Sedimentary basins host significant geothermal energy resources that can produce both direct heat and electric

power from water in the temperature range 50-150 °C. The Molasse Sedimentary Basin in Germany shows the potential of this type of geothermal resource with annual returns of 530 GWh from direct use and 36 GWh from power production (*Agemar et al. 2014*). Similar development could be made in the Western Canadian Sedimentary Basin (WCSB) and the first such geothermal power plant is currently being developed in Estevan, Saskatchewan using a geothermal resource discovered during oil-and-gas exploration (*Coleman 2019*). Two additional projects are under development in Greenview and Rocky Mountain House, Alberta. The WCSB covers a large portion of western Canada and encompasses both remote areas and urban districts. This diversity makes it possible to develop a wide variety of geothermal applications, from commercial generation of electricity to direct use of the heat for heating homes, greenhouses, and industrial processing.

Development in the WCSB has benefitted from extensive geological and geophysical datasets collected for oil-and-gas exploration, some of which are in the public domain. Previous studies have quantified the thermal structure of the WCSB using well-log information (*Palmer-Wilson et al. 2018*). These estimates could be improved with additional information in areas where borehole data is not available. This research aims to extend previous methods of geothermal assessment by utilizing electromagnetic geophysics to measure resistivity between and below boreholes which give better estimates of the geothermal resources.

Resistivity is an important parameter in geothermal exploration because it is sensitive to the amount and salinity of subsurface fluids. Resistivity can be measured from surface exploration with methods such as magnetotellurics and airborne electromagnetics (*Muñoz 2014*). However, like all geophysical data, the resulting models suffer from non-uniqueness.

In the context of the WCSB, the basic resistivity structure is a low resistivity layer of sedimentary rocks (1-100 ohm-m) that is up to 5 km thick and which overlies a high resistivity basement (over 1000 ohm-m). Magnetotelluric data produce a model that does not

always reliably image internal structure within the basin, or the increase in resistivity at the base. However other measurements of resistivity are available in this area and include well logs and airborne EM surveys. The goal of the research in this paper is to combine these various methods for measuring subsurface resistivity and develop an improved model that can guide geothermal exploration.

In this study we investigate this approach in the Peace River area in Northwestern Alberta where there are a number of potential users for geothermal heat (see Fig. 1). At this location the WCSB is between 4-5 km thick, and it can be divided into two main electrical-stratigraphic groups. The upper layer is a low resistivity Cretaceous sandstone which overlays more resistive Paleozoic carbonates. Both overlay a highly resistive Pre-Cambrian crystalline basement. Estimates of temperature showed that the temperatures within the basin may be not high enough to produce electricity and is therefore more appropriate for direct use (Banks and Harris, 2018). The Helmholtz Alberta Initiative, which funded the magnetotelluric data acquisition in the Peace River area, was investigating the possible use of heat from these aquifers in oil sands processing. The temperature of the crystalline basement may be high enough for electricity generation, but would require engineered geothermal systems to fracture crystalline rock to develop a geothermal reservoir. However, drilling into crystalline rock is expensive. Reducing exploration risk by imaging the basement structure is vital for the development of this resource.

Fig. 1. Map of Alberta with Peace River highlighted by the yellow star

2. Methods

This research is focussed on magnetotelluric (MT) exploration, which is an electromagnetic method using naturally occurring radio waves to measure subsurface

resistivity. By using natural electromagnetic signals, this method is capable of deeper exploration than other EM methods. Subsurface resistivity is imaged by measuring orthogonal electric and magnetic fields at the surface. The ratio of these fields determines the resistivity structure of the subsurface as a function of frequency. Lower frequencies measure deeper in the Earth. The data are then inverted using the Rodi and Mackie (2001) 2D inversion code to find a model that fits the data. In the absence of other information, the inversion seeks the smoothest resistivity model consistent with the data.

If other types of data are available to constrain subsurface resistivity, they can be included in the inversion process. With well logs, they can be assembled to produce a model of near surface structure. This can be used in the inversion through a range of strategies.

3. Magnetotelluric and well log data

The University of Alberta acquired a 67 station MT survey along two profiles in the Peace River area highlighted in Figure 1. The goal was to characterize the structure of the sedimentary basin and underlying crystalline basement as part of the Helmholtz-Alberta Initiative. This project investigated whether geothermal heat could be used as a heat source for the extraction and processing of oilsands and heavy oil (Majorowicz et al., 2013; Hofmann et al., 2014).

Well log data is also available in this area with more than 600,000 well-log files from the Alberta Energy Regulator. Over 10,000 of these well-logs are in the Peace River area and 2,926 of these contain resistivity log data. The well-log data were smoothed using a moving median filter in order to reduce noise while preserving sharp changes in resistivity caused by changes in lithology (see Fig 2).

Fig. 2. Well-log resistivity data from the Peace River area

4. Results and Discussion

To incorporate the well-log data a separate resistivity model was constructed. The well-logs located within 15 km of the northern profile were identified (Fig 3) and projected onto the profile (Fig 4.i). The resistivity values within 50m vertically and 15km along the profile were averaged onto the inversion model mesh (Fig 4.ii).

The inversion method used in this study finds a resistivity model which fits the data and is also as smooth as possible. The unconstrained model is shown in Figure 5.i and it can be seen that low resistivity layer in the upper 2 km is well imaged. However, the base of this layer is smoothed to depth as a consequence of the physics of MT and the inversion process.

Fig. 3. Map view of the northern MT profile with the well logs used to create the model in Fig 4.i highlighted.

Constraining the inversion using the resistivity model in Figure 4.ii was found to more than double the misfit. This is likely due to the heterogeneity of the near surface close to the stations. By constraining the upper most portion of the model, the inversion loses the flexibility to accommodate for this variability. As a result, the model is constrained below a depth of 300 m. The comparison of inversion results are shown in Figure 5 with i) the unconstrained inversion, ii) the constrained inversion, and iii) the discontinuous inversion. This discontinuity, or tear, in the inversion model in Fig 5.iii was chosen at 2km based on the resistive layer in the well-log data (Fig 4i). All models were run with the same inversion parameters. The constrained model has a lower misfit and shows a contrast in resistivity in the depth range of 2-3 km. This is likely the transition between sandstones and carbonates.

Fig. 4. Incorporating well-log resistivity data into the MT inversion. i) Well-log data projected onto the inversion mesh. ii) Well-log resistivity model created by averaging data points.

Fig. 5. Comparisons of 2-D MT inversion results: i) unconstrained with hypothetical boundaries annotated, ii) constrained from 300m surface to depth of 2.4 km and iii) with smoothing requirement relaxed at a depth of 2 km for the transition from Cretaceous to Paleozoic rocks

5. Future Work

The goal of this research is to determine how information from resistivity logs can improve the reliability and resolution of models derived from MT inversion in a sedimentary basin such as the WCSB.

Once the near surface layer is properly incorporated, we will use the extensive well-log database to create a near surface resistivity model of Alberta and use this to constrain the MT inversion from Wang et al. (2018). This will allow us to create a more reliable model of the resistivity structure of the WCSB and underlying basement in Alberta.

6. Acknowledgments

We would like to thank the Alberta Energy Regulator for access to the well-log database as well as the Helmholtz Alberta Initiative for funding the magnetotelluric acquisition.

We would also like to acknowledge that the University of Alberta is situated on Treaty 6 territory, traditional lands of First Nations and Métis people.

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Geothermal Potential of Closed Underground Mines: Con Mine Study (Northwest Territories, Canada)

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Abstract

The abandoned and flooded Con Mine has been considered as a potential geothermal resource since its closure in 2003. The objective of this research is to provide a revised estimate of the geothermal potential of the abandoned Con Mine. An improved analytical approach, based on an energy balance calculation, for estimating the geothermal energy contained in a flooded underground mine is presented. The analytical method is based on the finite line source equation which considers cooled or heated mine tunnels as heat sources or sinks, with a constant heat exchange rate. For the calculations, the underground mine geometry is simplified to a linear heat source of equivalent length and fixed radius. The preliminary results obtained with this approach are a geothermal potential of 2.72 MW for heating and 1.59 MW for cooling for a period of time of 25 years. The results of this approach are to be compared to those obtained with a numerical model for the estimation of geothermal resources. The analytical approach will be further improved to reproduce more representative numerical results.

1. Introduction

Mining environments store geothermal heat from the Earth's natural heat flow. It is a sensitive heat storage medium, because the energy is released as temperature decreases without change of state. The amount of thermal energy is proportional to the storage volume, the heat capacity of the materials and temperature decrease of the material storing the heat (Muffler & Cataldi, 1978). Mining tunnels allow pumping at high water flow rates to extract or inject significant energy. However, the implementation of a geothermal energy project requires knowledge of the geothermal potential of the site. Since its closure, the abandoned and flooded Con Mine (Figure 1) has been considered as a geothermal resource because of the amount of water contained in the mine. Moreover, the water temperature can reach 30 °C at about 1 km depth (Ghomshei, 2007). This interest prompted this new research project. The objective is to provide a revised

estimate of the geothermal potential of the abandoned Con Mine. We aim to improve analytical approaches through a resource estimate based on an energy balance calculation for estimating the geothermal energy contained in a flooded mine, using the Con Mine as an example.

The largest gold production in the Yellowknife area was from the Con and Giant mines. The Con Mine was developed in the Yellowknife Greenstone Belt and is located in the Slave Geological Province (Figure 2). The Greenstone Belt is bounded to the west by younger granitic rocks of the Western Plutonic Complex (Figure 3). The belt consists of a succession of mafic to intermediate volcanic rocks with small inclusions of volcanoclastic and sedimentary rocks to the northeast. The rocks underlying the Con Mine dip 70-80° to the southeast (Miramar Con Mine Ltd, 2007). Gold mineralization is hosted in shear zones and this is where mining was focused. The shear zones are predominantly composed of chlorite-carbonate schist with increasing sericite, sulphide and quartz content in the areas of higher gold mineralization (Miramar Con Mine Ltd, 2007).

Figure 1. Con Mine location. Background image taken from Google Earth 2021.

Legend

- | | |
|--|--|
| Arctic Continental Shelf | Arctic Platform |
| Churchill province | Bear province |
| Cordilleran Orogen | Innuitian Orogen |
| Interior Platform | Slave province |
| Oceanic Crust | NWT Geopolitical Boundary |

Figure 2. Map of the geological provinces of the Northwest Territories (modified from Northwest Territories Geological Survey, 2021).

2. Methods

Estimating the energy content of the mine water with an energy balance calculation is based on the water volume in the mine and the initial and final water temperature expected when the system is exploited for geothermal heating or cooling. It is a conservative approach which assumes that the mine water reservoir is a closed flow system; more realistically, water can flow inside and outside of the mine (Bao et al., 2019). Then, the energy transferred from the surrounding rock mass to the water by means of conductive heat transfer can be determined

Legend

- | | |
|---|---|
| Gabbro Sills | Shear Zones |
| Granite | Townsite Formation Dacite |
| Massive and Pillow Basalt | Slave Craton Faults NWT |
| Slave Craton mafic | Slave Craton Lineaments NWT |

Figure 3. Detailed geological map of the vicinity of Con Mine site (modified from Northwest Territories Geological Survey, 2021).

by the potential temperature response of the mine shafts, drifts and workings when water temperature inside the mine is lowered or increased. Here, we consider the total volume of water after the mine workings have closed and being flooded by water.

The materials considered for the volume method to assess the geothermal resource are the water flooding the mine and the surrounding host rock. The equation below is used to evaluate the energy contained in a volume of water when its temperature is lowered or increased:

$$E_w = v_w \times (T_w - T_m) \times c_w \quad (1)$$

where E_w [MJ] is the energy content, v_w [m³] is the volume of water, T_w [K] is the initial temperature of water, T_m [K] is the maximum or minimum temperature at which the material can be cooled or heated and c_w [MJ m⁻³ K⁻¹] is the volumetric heat capacity of water.

The energy content E_w is converted to power by taking into account the time of exploitation:

$$P_w = \frac{E_w}{t} \quad (2)$$

where P_w is the power [W] and t is the time [s].

Determining the energy available from the rock mass requires an evaluation of the temperature changes in the surrounding medium when water in the underground mine is cooled or heated to T_m as a result of heat extraction or injection. The finite line source (FLS) solution was used to determine the temperature distribution in the rock mass. The equivalent length of the mine tunnels was considered as the length of the heat source when applying the FLS. Since the Con Mine volume is composed of shafts and drifts with irregular geometry, this volume was transformed into an equivalent mine tunnel length with the formula of a cylindrical volume (Figure 4) in order to keep the same volume. For this calculation, we didn't take into account the surface roughness since only conductive heat transfer is simulated.

The temperature response from a linear heat source of finite length surrounded by a solid medium with conductive heat transfer was reviewed by Philippe et al. (2009) and this formulation was used in this study :

$$Q = \lambda_s * \frac{T_0 - T_m}{G_{FLS}(Fo^*, r/H, D/H)} \quad (3)$$

where r [m] is the mine tunnel radius, Q [W] is the total heat exchange rate, λ_s [$W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$] is the average thermal conductivity of the bedrock determined in the laboratory, H [m] is the mine tunnel length, D [m] is the distance from the surface to the upper end of the source, T_0 [$^{\circ}C$] is undisturbed ground temperature, T_m [$^{\circ}C$] is the final temperature of the medium, $Fo^* = Fo/\tilde{r}^2$ [-] is a normalized Fourier (Fo) number, $\tilde{r} = r/t_b$ is the dimensionless radius [-] and G_{FLS} is the thermal response function of the finite line source or G-function.

Figure 4. Concept of the application of the Finite Line Source method to the Con Mine.

Note that, with this method, the energy is extracted or injected with a constant heat exchange rate during the time fixed in order to evaluate the power from the rock. The total power available (from water and rock) during the time of operation is the summation of P_w and Q . The coefficient of performance (COP) of the system is considered to assess the energy available to be provided to buildings.

3. Results

An average temperature of the mine's water of $26\ ^{\circ}C$ has been assumed. According to the geothermal gradient, a temperature value at each 100 m has been calculated. Then, we have calculated the average of these temperatures. This mine water temperature is decreased to evaluate the heating potential and increased to evaluate the cooling potential. With the heating and cooling thermal power from the analytical model, it is possible to determine the extraction rate and the efficiency of the operation (Table 1).

Table 1. Parameters used for the calculation of the heating and cooling power.

Parameter	Heating	Cooling
Time [years]	25	
Water volume [m^3]	917 080	
Initial temperature T_0 [$^{\circ}C$]	26	26
Final temperature T_m [$^{\circ}C$]	2	40
COP	3.56	5.7
Power from water [MW]	0.12	0.07
Power from Rock [MW]	2.6	1.52
Total power [MW]	2.72	1.59
Pumping rate [m^3/s]	0.027	0.027
Efficiency [%]	70	53

According to the results of Table 1, we can evaluate the number of different infrastructure (e.g., school, hospital, hotel) that can benefit from this energy. The needs in heating and cooling of different infrastructure have been assessed thanks to the database of the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE). This database provides essential information about buildings located in Denver, USA. We took those simulation files of archetype buildings and made simulations in the Yellowknife weather conditions with the EnergyPlus software. Therefore, we have been able to assess the needs in heating and cooling under Yellowknife's climatic conditions.

Figure 5 presents the number of buildings that can be heated with geothermal heat pumps fed by the mine water of the Con Mine site. As there is a large component associated with the large office category, it's difficult to

appreciate other installations in Figure 5. **Error! Reference source not found.** Therefore, Figure 6 excludes large offices. It seems that large offices have some internal gains which allow them to reduce the energy needed to heat the medium. This can be an explanation for the large number of large offices.

Figure 5. Number of units of each infrastructure that can be heated with heat pump systems using the mine water.

Figure 6. Detailed number of units of each infrastructure (without the large office) that can be heated with heat pump systems using the mine water.

4. Discussion

The power obtained from this analytical model shows that there is a fair potential in heating and cooling using the mine waters. Nevertheless, the results obtained with the analytical approach should be confirmed by a second approach, the numerical one, deemed more representative of the mine geometry. By comparing the two approaches, we will know if the analytical approach is underestimating or overestimating the heating and cooling potential.

The number of theoretical building units is promising. However, it must be emphasized that not all shown uses in Figure 5 are practicable on the Con Mine site. In addition, there are many technical and economic constraints. For example, the initial construction cost of a district heating system can be important if infrastructure to carry water out of the site is needed.

5. Conclusions

This analytical approach used to evaluate the Con Mine geothermal potential took into account the energy contained in the water, and the heat transferred from the rock to water. This approach gave a total power of 2.72 MW in heating and 1.59 MW in cooling over 25 years of operation. The results of this approach will be compared with those obtained with a numerical model for the estimation of geothermal resources, also for the Con Mine. The analytical approach will be improved to reproduce the numerical results deemed more representative.

6. Acknowledgments

The support of the Northwest Territories Geological Survey and Geological Survey of Canada is acknowledged.

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Combined geological and petrophysical characterization of the rocks to the West and Northwest of the Nevado del Ruiz volcano (NRV)

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Keywords: Thermal conductivity, Porosity, Permeability, Colombia, Geothermal energy.

Abstract

This work presents an analysis of the geological context combined with thermal and hydraulic properties of rock samples collected to the west and northwest of the Nevado del Ruiz volcano (NRV), Colombia. Permeability, porosity, and thermal conductivity were measured. A total of 164 laboratory analyses were performed on Cajamarca complex (Pes), Pre-Ruiz lava flow (CL-PRE), and Andesite (NgQa) rock samples, representing the potential reservoir and cap rock of the geothermal system. An inferred geological cross-section was elaborated based on structural geology measurements to show the location and the contacts of the main lithologies. Laboratory analyses indicate that NgQa is the most permeable lithology (4.3 mD), while Pes the least permeable (0.02 mD); CL-PRE shows the highest porosity (9.0%) and Pes the highest thermal conductivity ($2.87 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$). These results confirm the necessity of further studies to assess secondary porosity features such as fractures, which plays a key role in fluid flow patterns in the geothermal system of the NRV.

1. Introduction

The commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, in addition to the oil crises of recent years, have forced countries to migrate to non-conventional renewable energies, lower generation costs, and greater energy security over time (UN, 2020). Colombia has one of the cleanest energy matrices in the world: in 2018, 68.4% of the installed capacity came from hydroelectric generation. However, its high dependence on water resources makes Colombia vulnerable to critical hydrological scenarios (Arango, 2019). Thanks to its location along the Pacific Ring of Fire, the country has an important and sizeable potential for geothermal energy generation (Marzolf, 2014). The current geothermal potential for electricity generation is equivalent to approximately 7% (1195.24 MW) of the country's installed capacity in 2020, but could be higher (Alfaro et al., 2020).

The department of Caldas is currently the most geothermally studied area in the country, because of its numerous active volcanoes, such as the NRV (ISAGEN, 2014). Its recent eruptive history and the presence of several superficial manifestations are the evidence of the existence of geothermal resources with adequate characteristics for electricity generation. In 1983, the first pre-feasibility study for the geothermal development of the NRV was conducted, followed by the first exploratory well (Nereidas I), drilled in 1997 to the west of the volcano. Hydrothermal alteration zoning suggested the presence of a high temperature system (Monsalve et al., 1998). In 2012, a first conceptual geothermal exploration model with potential zones of heat source and fluid circulation were proposed to the northwest of the NRV (Mejía et al., 2012). NW-SE oriented structures along with longitudinal NE-SW oriented faults are believed to play an important role for fluid flow due to their distending character (Mejía et al., 2012). Structures such as faults and fractures control the direction and drainage of thermal fluid emanations (Diaz & Aguirre, 2014).

This paper seeks to contribute to the characterization of the NRV geothermal reservoir at the intersection between the Nereidas, Cueva-Pirineos, and La Tosca-El Descanso faults based on 1) an inferred geological cross-section, and 2) petrophysical characterization of rock samples collected at outcrops.

2. Methods

2.1. Rock sampling and geological profile

Four field campaigns permitted collection of 21 rock samples in the area located NW of the NRV around the Botero-Londoño hot springs, close to the Nereidas I well and to the intersection between the three faults mentioned above. This area is presumed to have greater geothermal importance due to the numerous thermal manifestations and high temperature found in hot springs. A geological cross-section was drawn (Figure 1; AA') based on field observations. It begins in the northwest of the NRV at the La Tosca-El Descanso fault (A), where outcrops of glacial deposits (M) are observed;

it extends to the southeast where the Playa Larga debris avalanche deposits (DA-PL), the Playa Larga Eruptive unit (UE-PL), and the Pre-Ruiz lava flows (CL-PRE) at the Cueva-Pirineos fault are observed (A'). All samples

taken for laboratory analysis were collected at outcrops, except the core from the Nereidas I well that was provided by CHEC (Central Hidroelectrica de Caldas).

Figure 1. Map of the study area to the NW of the NRV.

2.2. Thermal conductivity and diffusivity assessment

Thermal conductivity (TC) and thermal diffusivity (TD) assessments were performed at the Open Geothermal Laboratory of the Institut national de la recherche scientifique in Quebec City, QC, Canada (Raymond et al., 2017). The samples were prepared for measurements with a thermal conductivity scanner by cutting a flat surface. The samples were additionally dried in an oven at 110°C for approximately 72h. A layer of black paint was applied to the flat surface of each sample to ensure the absorption of infrared waves during the measurement. The rock samples and the equipment standard were left at room temperature overnight prior to the measurement to ensure that the temperature difference between the

samples was only due to the heating process of the equipment. First, the sensors were calibrated with standard samples. Then, the appropriate standards (fused quartz and titanium alloy samples) were selected for comparative analysis with the rock samples of unknown thermal properties, according to the suggestion of the manual for natural materials. The measurement mode allowing for the evaluation of both thermal conductivity and diffusivity was chosen. The thermal properties determined along scan lines were narrowed by eliminating the data at the sample boundaries to avoid atypical values due to boundary effects.

A FOX-50 device was additionally used to evaluate thermal conductivity, using the guarded heat flow meter

technique to determine the impact of temperature changes (Miranda et al., 2018). The instrument consists of two plates, two heat flow meters and two protective casings to prevent heat losses. Measurements were verified with a pyrex standard and the analysis were made under the following temperature conditions (20, 60, 100, 130, 160 °C). The samples were cut into a cylindrical shape with both sides polished. They were placed in an oven at 110°C for 72h and cooled at room temperature. A film of silicone paste of about 0.1 mm was smeared on both samples surfaces to improve the contact between rock sample and heating plates. Finally, the data obtained were corrected for sample thickness.

2.3. Heat capacity estimation

Heat capacity is the ability of a material to store heat and is affected by the proportion of matrix versus the gas or liquid filling the pores (Clauser, 2006). The volumetric heat capacity c ($J\ kg^{-1}\ K^{-1}$) was deduced from the assessment of thermal conductivity and diffusivity from TCS using the Debye equation (Homuth et al., 2015):

$$c = \lambda / \rho \kappa$$

where λ is the thermal conductivity ($W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$), ρ is the density of the rock ($kg\ m^{-3}$) and κ is the thermal diffusivity ($m^2\ s^{-1}$). Assessment of thermal conductivity and heat capacity was made at dry state such that heat capacity was calculated for dry conditions.

Figure 2. Representative core samples from the study area at the NRV. (A) andesitic porphyry with a low to moderate porous matrix made up of quartz, plagioclase and some amphiboles, belonging to the CL-PRE formation in the Cueva Pirineos area. (B) Metamorphic rock belonging to the quartz member of Pes next to the Nereidas creek at the Botero Londoño area. (C) Andesite (volcanic rock) with a porous matrix having amphibole and plagioclase crystals. (D) Metamorphic rock belonging to the quartz member of Pes in low fractured zone. (E) Rock of Quebradagrande complex (Kvc) volcanic member (metamorphic origin) composed of basalts, pyroclastic flows and diabasic dikes. (F) Representative rock of Pes's graphitic schist member located at the Barro Azul zone, influenced by the San Jerónimo fault; rock with quartz veins presence and overall graphite.

2.4. Permeability and porosity assessment

Permeability and porosity analysis were performed with the AP-608 Automated Permeameter-Porosimeter, which is a system for inferring gas permeability using Darcy's law and the pressure decay method as well as porosity using the Boyle's law (Raymond et al., 2017). The exact dimensions (diameter, height, weight) of each cylindrical sample (Figure 2) were initially evaluated. The equipment was configured for a measurement at 3448 kPa with nitrogen gas and the measurement for porosity and permeability was activated. The range of measurement for permeability of the equipment ranges from 0.001 mD to 10 D (Raymond et al., 2017) and the Klinkenberg correction for gas slippage effect was made.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Geological cross section

A geological cross section was made with information from the Cueva-Pirineos fault with a dip of 70 °NW as observed in the field and previously documented by Ossa (2018) and the La Tosca-El Descanso fault with a dip of 80°NW, again verified in the field and previously documented by Ceballos (2017) (Figure 3). The Pes unit was found until approximately 750 - 1200 m depth according to the data from the stratigraphic column of the Nereidas I well (Monsalve et al., 1998; Ossa, 2018). The CL-PRE unit is made of lava flows with an andesite and basalt composition that can be locally dacitic and it has an approximate thickness of 574 m and lies directly in contact with Pes (Ossa, 2018).

The DA-PL outcrops in the Nereidas and Playa Larga sectors are found with an approximate thickness of 50 m (Martínez et al., 2014) to the W of the NRV, between the basins of the Nereidas creek and the Molinos river (Martínez et al., 2014). The DA-PL unit fills the topography with glacial morphology related to moraines and forming mounds suppressed in discordant contact to the CL-PRE in the Nereidas sector (Martínez et al., 2014). Moraines (M) are observed near the surface overlying lava flows and pyroclastic deposits, such as debris and avalanches (DA-PL) associated with different development periods of the NRV Complex and corresponding to the ages after the maximum glacial advance that took place 0.035 Myr ago (Martínez et al., 2014); the M units have an approximate thicknesses of 30 – 40 m, extended to the northwest of the NRV, in the Azufrado and Nereidas ravine basins (Martínez et al., 2014). The UE-PL outcrops along the Nereidas creek, between the haciendas of Las Nereidas and La Vega, are identified as a matrix-supported, stratified deposit with a

variable thickness of 2 – 3 m (Martínez et al., 2014; Ceballos, 2017).

Figure 3. Cross section NW of the NRV. The geological profile is marked with a red line and the sampled points are marked by dotted square. The dextral fault movement is identified with continuous black lines and the sinistral fault movement with black lines having dots in the middle. The sampling points have colors that represent each lithology to which they are associated. UE-PL unit is not shown because its thickness is negligible at the considered scale.

3.2. Laboratory measurement

3.2.1. Thermal conductivity and diffusivity assessment and heat capacity estimation

The arithmetic mean and the median of thermal properties associated to each lithology were calculated (Table 1). The median allowed to determine an average property value for each lithology. Using the median over the mean excludes values that are far from the average. This is important for the Pes unit having important mineralogical variations.

CL-PRE is the lithology with the lowest thermal conductivity and diffusivity, while Pes is the one with the highest values (Table 1). CL-PRE has the least significant variation amongst all samples. However, this unit is the one including the fewest samples analyzed. Pes also had the most important variation of thermal conductivity, with a minimum of $1.70 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and a maximum of

$4.15 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The inferred heat capacity is about $2.3 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the study area (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean and median thermal properties for each lithology of rock samples collected at NRV.

Lithologic Unit	Number of samples	λ ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)		κ ($\text{mm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)		C ($\text{MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	
		Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Mean	Median
Pes	33	2.6	2.3	1.1	1.0	2.5	2.4
NgQa	13	1.1	0.9	0.9	0.6	1.5	1.8
CL-PRE	3	1.5	1.5	0.7	0.7	2.0	2.0
Kvc	2	2.4	2.3	1.0	1.0	2.4	2.5
Ksc	7	1.9	1.9	0.7	0.7	2.9	3.2

TC changes according to the mineral content of the material and its porosity, explaining the different ranges of values for different lithologies. The Pes contains two members, one with a high quartz content and the other with a high graphite content. The one with high quartz content has a more important TC, in agreement with the literature (Clauser, 2006; Clauser, 2011).

The NgQa and the CL-PRE, both extrusive igneous rocks, are similar in composition, because CL-PRE comes from a combination of andesite and dacite rocks. However, the NgQa has a higher porosity and a lower quartz content (Figure 6), which explains the differences in TC.

Figure 4. Thermal conductivity at different temperature for Pes (square), Kvc (triangle), NgQa (cross), and CL-PRE (circle).

The TC in metamorphic rocks decreases with the increase in temperature; however, the quartz content and the porosity of the sample can change this behaviour (Clauser, 2006). Figure 4 illustrates the observed TC behaviour in relation to the temperature increase. For the Pes unit, the three samples were collected from three different zones around the study area. The P2 sample is located closest to the NRV (Figure 1), where the highest density of hydrothermal activity is evidenced by fumaroles and hot springs near the Quebrada Negra and the Nereidas faults. The P13 sample is from an area

outside the volcanic complex, providing a comparison of the different areas of Pes. N3_Techo is a sample from the Nereidas I well at a depth of 1.3 km.

For the Pes unit, only the sample collected at depth shows a TC increase with increasing temperature, which is atypical, while the other two samples collected at outcrops (P2 and P13) show a TC decreasing with temperature as expected (Figure 4). P13 has a higher TC variation with respect to temperature, which can be associated to a different mineralogical content.

The samples from the CL-PRE unit show different trends for TC as function of temperature, especially sample P4. Each sample has a different degree of meteorization affecting the mineralogy, which can generate changes in thermal properties, such as TC (Tarbuck et al., 2005).

3.2.2. Permeability and porosity assessments

Metamorphic and unfractured igneous rocks have a permeability range of approximately $1\text{E-}20\text{ m}^2$ to $1\text{E-}17\text{ m}^2$ ($1\text{E-}5\text{ mD}$ to 0.01 mD) (Freeze & Cherry, 1979). Within the study area, the lithology with the highest permeability is the NgQa (Figure 5), ranging from $4.72\text{E-}16\text{ m}^2$ to $2.57\text{E-}14\text{ m}^2$ (0.478 mD to 26.06 mD). Pes samples have a permeability range from $9.87\text{E-}19\text{ m}^2$ to $9.97\text{E-}15\text{ m}^2$ (0.001 mD to 10.10 mD). Some of the samples analyzed contain thin fractures, which can generate higher permeability (Moreno et al., 2018). CL-PRE samples have permeability within the same range as the Pes unit, showing a notable difference with the NgQa unit in spite of both being extrusive rocks.

The metamorphic rocks showed the highest thermal conductivity compared to the other rock types, due to their high quartz content. Globally, the basement of the system has an average heat capacity. In general, no inconclusive data was found for the reports of thermal properties per sample or lithology. Despite having extreme values outside the average, the data is representative of the lithologies, as a consequence of the changes in the mineral composition of the rocks such as Pes, with its two members, quartz and schist. Extrusive igneous rocks showed differences in permeability, with lavas being the least permeable, having values similar to those of Pes. The study area of the NRV presents rocks with a low matrix permeability associated to primary porosity. Fractures observed in the field in rocks near the Nereidas, Cueva-Pirineos, and Tosca-El Descanso faults can increase permeability and it is recommended to conduct in situ permeability tests, which can allow to consider the effect of secondary porosity features such as fractures. The Pes unit is of great interest in this study because it is considered to host the geothermal resources

despite its low matrix permeability of $1.53\text{E-}16\text{ m}^2$, but with the highest TC of $2.87\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Figure 5. Permeability of rock samples collected at NRV. The yellow part represent quartile one and the blue corresponds to the third quartile and together are the 50% of the data. The dividing line between both colors represents the median value.

Figure 6. Porosity of rock samples collected at NRV. The yellow color represents quartile one and the blue color represents quartile three and together are the 50% of the data. The dividing line between both colors represents the median value.

4. Conclusions

According to the results of the hydraulic properties of the rock, the dominant heat transfer mechanism is conduction. However, the evidence of hydrothermal emanations, field observations, type of extrusive and pyroclastic magmatism suggest the existence of a hydrothermal system, where the heat transfer mechanism would be convection along fault planes. Since the system has a fractured basement, secondary permeability measurements are required to better characterize this behaviour.

The rock thermophysical properties quantified here will be useful to make an improved conceptual model of the NDR geothermal field. Further in-depth characterizations of TC and radiogenic elements will be required for the estimation of the heat flow in the area. In addition, aquisition of structural geology data appears necessary to determine the impact of the faults on potential fluid flow paths.

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